

AMBIENT-6G

Towards standardized 6G connectivity for ambient-powered energy-neutral IoT devices

Deliverable D3.1

Initial Report on Low-power 6G Network Protocols

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Abstract:

This deliverable (D3.1) presents the initial research outcomes on techniques and protocols for ENDs and their integration into future 6G networks. It consolidates early investigations across multiple protocol layers, addressing the challenges posed by devices operating with intermittent and extremely constrained energy resources. At PHY, novel synchronization, modulation, and waveform designs are analyzed to reduce complexity and power consumption, while backscatter and symbiotic communication techniques are examined with emphasis on signal modeling, interference management, and hardware-level integration. The study also explores RF charging mechanisms, with results showing efficiency gains from distributed multi-antenna architectures and highlighting the importance of hardware-protocol co-design. At higher layers, MAC and RRC innovations are introduced, including energy-aware and lightweight channel access and scheduling, and supporting frameworks. Furthermore, network-level concepts are introduced for optimized architecture management and goal/context-aware scheduling, alongside initial security-by-design frameworks tailored to ultra-constrained devices. Overall, the deliverable establishes the technical basis for the development of lightweight 6G protocols that support sustainable and dependable operation of ENDs, paving the way for subsequent research and system integration activities.

Keywords:

backscattering communications, energy-neutral devices, lightweight 6G protocols, MAC, RF charging, RRC, security

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Executive Summary

This deliverable (D3.1) constitutes the first comprehensive outcome of WP3: Low-power 6th generation of cellular network technology (6G) network protocols and infrastructure within the AMBIENT-6G project. Its primary purpose is to establish the technical foundations for ultra-low-power and secure communication protocols that enable the integration of energy neutral devices (ENDs) into future 6G networks. For this, the deliverable discusses and innovates on physical layer (PHY) design, backscatter and symbiotic communications, wireless power transfer (WPT), medium access control (MAC)/Radio Resource Connection (RRC) protocol, device and edge interactions, and lightweight security mechanisms. Specifically,

- Chapter 2 investigates the evolution of the 3rd generation partnership project (3GPP) ambient IoT (A-IoT) PHY beyond Rel.19, introducing enhanced synchronization, modulation, and waveform optimization techniques, and exploring optical synchronization and symbol-synchronous networking for ultra-low-energy operation.
- Chapter 3 analyzes backscatter communication (BC) as a key enabler for END connectivity, presenting signal models, synchronization and modulation considerations, and practical approaches such as symbiotic radio and joint visible light communication (VLC)/BC.
- Chapter 4 focuses on radio frequency (RF)-WPT protocols and optimization, examining coherent and non-coherent charging schemes, the impact of waveform design on rectifier efficiency, and testbed-based insights for scalable, low-complexity implementations.
- Chapter 5 addresses MAC/RRC-level mechanisms for energy-adaptive END operation, including privacy protection, channel-access strategies, and realistic A-IoT simulation environments.
- Chapter 6 introduces intelligent network management concepts, including context/goal-aware protocols and enhancements to the A-IoT function (AIOTF) for dependable operations with minimal control-plane overhead.
- Chapter 7 establishes the security foundations for ENDs through a systematic threat analysis, energy-aware update and authentication mechanisms, and lightweight physical layer authentication (PLA) schemes suited to different device classes.

Collectively, these results directly contribute to the WP3 objective of enabling low-power 6G connectivity for ENDs, while complementing outcomes from other WPs. D3.1 exploits device-level constraints provided in D2.1 [1] and D2.2 [2], aligns with edge-computing perspectives from WP4, and provides technical inputs for validation and proof of concept (PoC) work in WP5. The deliverable sets the ground for subsequent protocol development (D3.2) and validation (D3.3).

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Glossary

3GPP 3rd generation partnership project.

5G 5th generation of cellular network technology.

6G 6th generation of cellular network technology.

A-IoT ambient IoT.

ACK acknowledgment.

AES advanced encryption standard.

AF application function.

AI artificial intelligence.

AIOTF A-IoT function.

AmBC ambient BC.

AoI age of information.

AP access point.

AWGN additive white Gaussian noise.

BC backscatter communication.

BD backscatter device.

BER bit error rate.

BF beamforming.

BPSK binary phase-shift keying.

BS base station.

BW bandwidth.

CAP clock acquisition part.

CDF cumulative distribution function.

CFO carrier frequency offset.

CIR channel impulse response.

CMOS complementary metal oxide semiconductor.

CN core network.

CoAP constrained application protocol.

CP cyclic prefix.

CRS cell-specific reference signal.

CSI channel state information.

CSS chirp spread spectrum.

CW continuous wave.

D2R device-to-reader.

DC direct current.

DDS direct digital synthesis.

DFD data flow diagram.

DFT discrete Fourier transform.

DL downlink.

DLI direct link interference.

DMA direct memory access.

DSSS direct-sequence spread spectrum.

DT decision transformers.

DTLS datagram transport layer security.

DUT device under test.

EdN edge node.

EH energy harvesting.

END energy neutral device.

ER energy receiver.

ESL electronic shelf label.

ET energy transmitter.

FFT fast Fourier transform.

FSK frequency shift keying.

FUG fast uplink grant.

GPIO general-purpose input/output.

IC integrated circuit.

ID identifier.

IF intermediate-frequency.

INR interference-to-noise ratio.

IoT Internet of Things.

IoT D IoT device.

IQ in-phase and quadrature.

ISM industrial, scientific and medical.

KNN K-nearest neighbor.

KPI key performance indicator.

LED light emitting diode.

LoRa long range.

LoRaWAN LoRa wide-area network.

LTE long term evolution.

LTE-M LTE for machine-type communications.

MAC medium access control.

MCU microcontroller unit.

MIMO multiple-input multiple-output.

ML machine learning.

MQTT message queuing telemetry transport.

MRT maximum ratio transmission.

MSE mean square error.

MTTF mean time to failure.

NACK negative ACK.

NB-IoT narrowband IoT.

NFC near-field communication.

NLDP non-linear dynamic process.

NR new radio.

OCDM orthogonal chirp division multiplexing.

OFDM orthogonal frequency-division multiplexing.

OOK on-off keying.

PAPR peak-to-average power ratio.

PCE power conversion efficiency.

PHY physical layer.

PLA physical layer authentication.

PoC proof of concept.

PRDCH physical reader to device channel.

PSD power spectral density.

PV photovoltaic.

PWM pulse width modulation.

QoS quality-of-service.

R-TAS R2D timing acquisition signal.

R2D reader-to-device.

RA random access.

RAN radio access network.

RE radio element.

RF radio frequency.

RFID radio frequency identification.

RFS radio-frequency source.

RIS reflective intelligent surface.

RL reinforcement learning.

RMa rural macro.

RPS random-phase sweeping.

RRC Radio Resource Connection.

RSS received signal strength.

RSSI RSS indicator.

RX receiver.

SA spectrum analyser.

SDR software-defined radio.

SFO sampling frequency offset.

SIP start indicator part.

SIR signal-to-interference ratio.

SISO single-input single-output.

SNR signal-to-noise ratio.

SRS sounding reference signal.

STC sense-then-charge.

TLS transport layer security.

TTI transmission time interval.

TX transmitter.

UE user equipment.

UL uplink.

UMa urban macro.

UMi urban micro.

UNB ultra-narrowband.

VLC visible light communication.

WPT wireless power transfer.

WuR wake-up radio.

Chapter 1

Introduction

Energy neutral devices (ENDs) are crucial for sustainable large-scale Internet of Things (IoT) deployments that rely on energy harvesting (EH), which eliminates the need for battery charging or replacement and significantly reduces maintenance and environmental impact. However, their limited and intermittent energy supply poses significant challenges for communication protocols, resource allocation, and security frameworks.

Existing cellular IoT solutions such as narrowband IoT (NB-IoT) and LTE-M provide partial support for low-power connectivity but fall short of addressing the stringent requirements and heterogeneity of END ecosystems. Indeed, the evolution of wireless networks towards 6th generation of cellular network technology (6G) requires rethinking connectivity solutions for ENDs, which operate under low and variable energy budgets.

Recently, 3rd generation partnership project (3GPP) has initiated work on new radio (NR) ambient IoT (A-IoT) in Rel.19, introducing support for backscatter-based ENDs. This represents a necessary and important step towards integrating ENDs into mainstream cellular systems. At the same time, further research is required to explore cross-layer protocol innovations, advanced energy-awareness, and integrated security mechanisms that go beyond the initial NR A-IoT baseline. In this context, AMBIENT-6G aims to contribute new insights and solutions that will not only drive forward the research frontier but also facilitate future standardization activities and accelerate the development of 6G IoT ecosystems.

Within WP3 of AMBIENT-6G, we pursue novel lightweight device and network protocols, radio frequency (RF) charging, adaptive scheduling and computing, and security-by-design mechanisms to meet 6G END ambitions. These innovations must achieve several orders of magnitude improvements in energy efficiency compared to current 3GPP low-power wide-area network standards while remaining scalable, secure, and cost-effective. This deliverable presents an initial approach to such protocols and infrastructures, laying the groundwork for the development of concrete protocol designs and key performance indicator (KPI) evaluations in subsequent deliverables.

1.1 Scope and objectives

D3.1 is the first WP3 deliverable. Its specific objectives are to:

- Investigate early design principles for lightweight communication, control, and operation protocols tailored to ENDS.
- Explore enabling technologies such as backscatter communication (BC), symbiotic radio, wireless power transfer (WPT) protocols, and intelligent duty-cycling and wake-up.
- Introduce security considerations suitable for the constraints of ENDS, laying the foundation for the subsequent security protocol framework.
- Exploit and contextualize the findings in relation to other AMBIENT-6G activities:
 - Leveraging device-level classes, assumptions, and models developed in WP2 (D2.1 and D2.2).
 - Complementing device-edge computing perspectives addressed in WP4 (D4.1).
 - Providing input to WP5 activities for system-level validation, KPI consolidation, and preparation of proof of concepts (PoCs).

The corresponding contributed technical content and discussions form a top-down pipeline from operation and physical layer (PHY) feasibility to network operation and security. Through these contributions, D3.1 delineates the initial technical landscape for low-power 6G protocols, ensuring alignment with the overall objectives of AMBIENT-6G and paving the way for measurable KPI achievement in later phases.

1.2 Structure of the document

The remainder of this deliverable is organized as follows.

Low-layer communication protocols for ENDS are covered in Chapters 2 and 3. Specifically, Chapter 2 introduces important PHY enablers for END communications. Therein, 3GPP A-IoT PHY evolution beyond Rel.19 is examined through improved, backward-compatible reader-to-device (R2D) frequency calibration handling and modulation. Machine learning (ML)-assisted waveform design is also considered for robust performance. Moreover, visible light communication (VLC)-based synchronization is examined as an electromagnetic interference-immune solution for precise indoor timing. At the same time, symbol-synchronous multi-hop strategies with instant relays and probabilistic sleeping are considered for dense deployments. Meanwhile, BC aspects are the focus of Chapter 3, which highlights the main related technical challenges and introduces a baseband-equivalent signal model to support system analysis. This chapter further discusses critical aspects such as synchronization, modulation, and hardware implementation, and considers practical approaches, including symbiotic radio architectures and joint visible light-backscatter schemes for energy-efficient integration into existing wireless systems.

Chapter 4 focuses on the RF charging technology, from low-layer to high-layer protocol aspects, addressing how the energy delivery can be optimized. The chapter shows that coherent beamforming (BF), relaxed synchronization, and channel state information (CSI)-free operation form the foundation for practical large-scale RF-WPT to END networks.

Chapters 5 and 6 continue with higher-layer communication and scheduling/operation related aspects of END networks. Specifically, Chapter 5 discusses medium access control (MAC) and Radio Resource Connection (RRC)-level design aspects for reliable operation of ultra-low-power

ENDs. It introduces energy-adaptive strategies for channel access and task scheduling, and provides initial validation results. This chapter ends with realistic channel modelling of A-IoT networks. Meanwhile, Chapter 6 presents protocols and architectures for goal/context-aware END activity scheduling that enhance system dependability with minimal control-plane overhead. Therein, performance evaluation results in representative use cases are presented and discussed, and also potential enhancements to the 3GPP-defined A-IoT function (AIOTF).

Chapter 7 focuses entirely on security aspects, outlining the initial security considerations for ENDs. It introduces a structured threat analysis framework to identify attack surfaces and categorize risks based on device capabilities and then presents energy-aware security update mechanisms for ENDs across four device classes. Moreover, physical layer authentication (PLA) strategies for ENDs in different BC scenarios are overviewed.

Together, these technical chapters provide interdependent building blocks for WP3's low-power 6G END protocols. Finally, the deliverable concludes with Chapter 8 summarizing the key findings and identifying the directions for the next deliverable.

Chapter 2

PHY layer design and procedures

This chapter examines PHY design choices for ENDS and respective ultra-low-power networks. First, we consider 3GPP A-IoT PHY and how it can evolve beyond the Rel.19 baseline. R2D synchronization is revisited, exposing carrier frequency offset (CFO) limitations for active devices, while we motivate modulation upgrades plus artificial intelligence (AI)/ML-driven waveform selection to improve robustness and efficiency while preserving backward compatibility. Next, we look into device synchronization over VLC, showing how optical links, implemented with small size components and immune to electromagnetic interference, can distribute accurate time/frequency indoors with practical bandwidth (BW)/power trade-offs in light emitting diodes (LEDs)/photodetectors and front-ends. Finally, we consider low-power symbol-synchronous communications, outlining instant-relay multi-hop with tailored window detectors and probabilistic sleeping to cut latency and energy in dense END deployments.

2.1 A-IoT PHY enhancements

This section focuses on potential enhancements to PHY design as conceived in 3GPP Rel.19 specification for A-IoT. We currently investigate limitations in synchronization and modulation aspects for the transmission link between the reader and the device, as well as ML-driven solutions for intelligent waveform optimization and selection.

2.1.1 R2D synchronisation & frequency calibration

In 3GPP Rel-19 A-IoT, the R2D link (essentially the downlink (DL) in legacy long term evolution (LTE)/NR) has been designed to be extremely simple for the device. Only a single physical channel (physical reader to device channel (PRDCH)) carries all downlink data (no separate physical downlink control channel or physical broadcast channel), and standard NR reference signals (demodulation reference signal, CSI-reference signal, etc.) are not used. Instead, a special preamble called the R2D timing acquisition signal (R-TAS) precedes each PRDCH burst to help the device identify the start of transmission and achieve timing sync before data. A simple sequence (called postamble) is also specified for transmission appended to PRDCH end, for the device to understand the end of transmission.

Rel-19 R-TAS consists of two parts [3]:

- start indicator part (SIP):** This part signals the start of PRDCH to the device. It is a known pattern consisting of two sequential ON/OFF symbols of different durations (i.e., a half-symbol ON then half OFF, followed by a quarter-symbol ON then 3/4 OFF) that ensures a unique signature/envelope for identification from a simple low-power envelope detector (supposed to achieve near-zero false alarm and <1% miss detection). Thus, SIP is defined by an 8-bit sequence (11001000) and consists of 4 consecutive on-off keying (OOK) “chips” each of duration $\frac{1}{4\Delta f}$ seconds during each orthogonal frequency-division multiplexing (OFDM) symbol. Essentially, we have 8 chips for SIP (bits are mapped one-to-one to chips) covering a fixed-length 2 OFDM symbols.
- clock acquisition part (CAP):** This part comes immediately after the SIP and it is used for clock calibration (the system is asynchronous) to let the device initially correct its clock speed to match the reader’s chip rate. PRDCH uses a discrete Fourier transform (DFT)-spread-OFDM based On-Off Keying waveform where multiple OOK chips can be packed into one 15 kHz OFDM symbol. Thus, CAP provides a way for the device to determine this chips-per-OFDM-symbol number on the fly by measuring the interval between the edges of a known ON/OFF pattern. CAP pattern is a short 4-bit sequence with two rapid ON/OFF transitions (1010). CAP uses the same allocation of “number of chips per OFDM symbol” M with PRDCH (Note: In Rel.19, M can vary among 2, 6, 12, 24 values to trade data rate versus robustness). So, essentially, there occur 2 transitions that should allow the device to measure the OOK “chip” duration and deduce the M value safely.

Figure 2.1: Rel.19 A-IoT R2D structure and device envelope view (case: M=2).

Using R-TAS Rel.19 design, a backscattering A-IoT tag (as is the so-called "Device 1" defined in 3GPP [4]¹) with only an envelope detector can reliably detect when an R2D transmission starts and lock onto the chip timing without any complex receiver processing.

However, current R-TAS design has a limitation: CFO is not explicitly handled. Rel-19 design has largely assumed that the downlink CFO was negligible or that any small residual offset could be tolerated over the short PRDCH burst. This assumption may hold for passive backscatter tags that don't generate their own RF, as their downlink (R2D) is just the reader's carrier which has no relative CFO. But active devices, such as the ones that have been agreed to study in

¹Device 1: around 1 μ W peak power consumption, has energy storage, initial sampling frequency offset (SFO) up to 10^X ppm (where X essentially defines the accuracy of the local clock frequency and is typically between values 4 and 5), neither R2D nor device-to-reader (D2R) amplification in the device. The device's D2R transmission is backscattered on a carrier wave provided externally.

Rel.20 [5] (Device 2b² and Device C³), will have independent transmit/receive oscillators, and CFO can be large, on the order of 1000–10000 ppm, i.e., it can be off by hundreds of kHz or even MHz-level in active devices without high-precision crystals. For example, at 900 MHz that translates to ± 900 kHz to 9 MHz frequency error, which is far too high for A-IoT small guard bands and simple envelope detectors.

The downside of such error is that the reader will have to assume a very large CFO and allocate wide receive filters/guard bands to support uplink (D2R). This approach will undermine D2R coverage and capacity for active tags (huge guard bands are spectrum-inefficient).

SIP is not enough: With 15 kHz sub-carrier spacing, an OFDM symbol is 66.7 μ s long in time. The longest continuous ON plateau in SIP is half a symbol (two initial chips), i.e., 33.4 μ s. SIP in total can give 33.4 + 17.6 μ s of ON chunks.

CAP is not enough: CAP provides only a very short glimpse of the signal in the frequency domain and was never intended as a frequency synchronization burst. For CAP, "best" case is for M=2, where we have two chunks (in each of the 2 OFDM symbols for CAP in that case) with total ON time of 33.4 + 33.4 μ s.

Indeed, 3GPP has noted that if separate local oscillators are used for transmitter (TX)/receiver (RX) in a device 2b, a reference frequency is needed, the R-TAS alone "may not be usable for CFO calibration". As a result, the Rel-20 "Study on enhancements for Ambient IoT in NR (outdoor active devices)" [5] has emphasized on improving synchronization and frequency calibration mechanisms to handle these active tags, and there is an ongoing study where designs with backward compatibility are needed. Our future work will investigate efficient solutions towards this direction.

2.1.2 R2D modulation

The specified R2D link in 3GPP Rel.19 uses OOK with Manchester line coding and no channel coding, enabling basic connectivity for indoor use cases (e.g., inventory, control commands) under controlled conditions. By analysing this design, however, we have identified certain limitations, especially considering the support of more capable active devices and/or outdoor scenarios:

- **Limited Downlink Range & Reliability:** Rel.19 R2D waveform lacks any forward-error correction mechanism or PHY repetition. In noisy outdoor channels with greater path loss, the uncoded OOK can suffer high error rates (even a single bit error causes a cyclic redundancy check failure with no chance of recovery).
- **No Frequency/Spatial Diversity:** R2D multiplexing is strictly in time (i.e., time division-multiple access) with a single wideband envelope signal. This means that the downlink has no mechanism to mitigate frequency-selective fading or narrowband interference that may be common in outdoor deployments. A deep fade or strong interferer can erase an OOK "ON" pulse entirely.

²Less than a few hundred μ W peak power consumption, with energy storage, intermediate-frequency (IF) envelope detector receiver or zero-IF receiver, SFO up to 10^Y ppm (where Y represents better accuracy than device 1, i.e., $Y < X$), R2D and/or D2R amplification in the device. Device's D2R transmission is generated internally.

³Between 1 mW and 10 mW peak power consumption, with energy storage, IF envelope detector receiver or zero-IF receiver, initial SFO up to 10^Y ppm, R2D and/or D2R amplification in the device. Device's D2R transmission is generated internally.

- **Basic Modulation Constrains Data:** While the simplistic Rel.19 OOK with Manchester line coding is deemed adequate for short commands or queries, it limits the data rate (Manchester doubles required BW for a given bit rate) that will be mostly needed in applications involving active A-IoT devices.
- **Basic Modulation Constrains Addressing:** Every A-IoT device must listen to all OOK transmissions and decode the address mask in the paging payload. This is an inefficient scheme in dense deployments where devices will be required to listen a much larger volume of unnecessary transmissions and more often.
- **Underutilization of Advanced Device Capabilities:** Active devices (such as 2b/C in Rel.20) are expected to have active RF components, small batteries/capacitors (supporting peak power on the order of 1–10 mW), and even low-power RF receivers (e.g. low-IF or zero-IF, according to study TR 38.769). They should be able to handle modest increases in complexity (not limited to pure envelope detection, e.g., may include a low-noise amplifier and an IF or direct-conversion receiver, for improved sensitivity). Current R2D design, however, does not take advantage of these advanced capabilities: it treats all devices as envelope-detector-based only.

Our future work will investigate solutions for efficient modulation enhancement that will address the limitations above for the emerging Rel.20 A-IoT devices and scenarios while allowing backward compatibility with Rel.19 passive devices and specification.

2.1.3 Intelligent waveform optimization

Intelligent waveform optimization and selection are pivotal for enabling ultra-low-power 6G networks, particularly for ENDs that rely on EH and BC. These devices, critical for applications like smart agriculture, require waveforms that minimize energy consumption while ensuring reliable communication. Traditional waveforms like OFDM used in 5th generation of cellular network technology (5G) suffer from high peak-to-average power ratio (PAPR), which increases power amplifier inefficiency and necessitates higher power back-off, making them unsuitable for battery-less IoT devices. In 6G, the goal is to achieve sub- μ W power levels for passive modes, leveraging backscatter-friendly designs that exploit ambient signals without active transmission. This part outlines AI/ML-driven solutions for intelligent waveform optimization and selection, addressing the open problem of high PAPR and enabling efficient, adaptive communication for ENDs in diverse 6G environments. Generally, intelligent waveform optimization and selection might be realized through the following AI/ML approaches:

- **Neural Network-Based Waveform Selection:** A deep learning model, such as a forward or recurrent neural network, is trained on real-time CSI and device energy profiles to dynamically select energy-efficient waveforms for ENDs. Candidate waveforms include ultra-narrowband (UNB) for minimal BW, orthogonal chirp division multiplexing (OCDM) for robustness in high-mobility scenarios, and direct-sequence spread spectrum (DSSS) for interference resistance. Inputs include CSI (e.g., channel gain, fading), EH rates (e.g., solar, RF), and traffic patterns, with the model outputting the optimal waveform to minimize PAPR and maximize efficiency. Training uses synthetic datasets reflecting 6G channel variability, with mean square error (MSE) loss to balance PAPR and inter-symbol interference. The deep learning model may operate at the network edge, processing real-time CSI from base stations (BSs) and energy profiles from ENDs. A multi-stage

classifier can layer decisions, first selecting waveform families (e.g., UNB vs. OCDM) and then fine-tuning parameters (e.g., chirp duration), improving adaptability over single-stage models. This aligns with 6G's requirement for scalable, energy-aware protocols in dense IoT deployments.

- **Reinforcement learning (RL) for Adaptive Waveform Optimization:** RL agents, such as deep Q-networks, optimize waveform parameters (e.g., pulse shape, modulation order) in real-time based on a reward function prioritizing low PAPR, high spectral efficiency, and regulatory compliance. The RL agent learns from interactions with the environment, including channel conditions, energy states, and interference levels, to adjust parameters like frequency-domain spectral shaping with spectrum extension. For example, frequency-domain spectral shaping spectrum extension with half-sine pulse achieves near-zero dB PAPR for $\pi/2$ -binary phase-shift keying (BPSK), reducing PAPR from 5.6 dB to 0.24–1.69 dB, yielding a 6 % power efficiency gain in hardware emulations. The RL agent can be deployed at the network edge or BS, using CSI and energy feedback from ENDS to update waveform policies. A feature control algorithm mitigates interference, enhancing coexistence with WiFi.
- **Auto-Encoder-Based Waveform Precoding:** Two-sided auto-encoder models optimize waveform precoding for uplink DFT spread OFDM (DFT-s-OFDM), reducing PAPR and enhancing coverage for ENDS. The encoder at the END preprocesses signals based on energy constraints, while the decoder at the BS reconstructs data, minimizing computational overhead. Pulses are represented in low-dimensional spaces (e.g., polynomial or Fourier bases) for scalability across block sizes. The auto-encoder may be integrated into END firmware and BS signal processing, leveraging lightweight neural architectures to minimize energy use. Training occurs offline, with periodic updates to adapt to channel variations.

These AI/ML solutions align with the goal of enabling battery-less IoT in 6G networks. Neural network-based selection and RL optimization reduce PAPR, addressing energy efficiency for ENDS. Auto-encoder precoding extends range, supporting dense deployments with more than 100 sensors per node with the minimum data delivery success of 95 %. These approaches contribute to an improvement in network efficiency and perpetual operation, aligning with emerging 6G standards for A-IoT.

2.2 Device synchronization over VLC link

A common clock reference enables simultaneous, time-correlated measurements between a set of devices and the generation of accurate RF frequencies and timing for inter-device communication. The power consumption of an accurate local oscillator can range from ~ 1 mW of a crystal oscillator to ~ 1 W of an oven controlled crystal oscillator and can be prohibitively large for an END. Additionally, the local oscillators would require a method to synchronize them. The generation and distribution of the clock reference from a central resource simplifies the construction of the ENDS and reduces their energy consumption.

In many systems, a reference frequency of 10 MHz is customary. Transmitting such a reference directly over RF is impractical in compact systems that may be of paramount importance in certain END applications. At 10 MHz, the free-space wavelength is on the order of 30 m, and efficient antennas therefore become physically large or, if made electrically small, suffer

significant efficiency and BW penalties. In addition, operation in the 5 MHz to 15 MHz range can conflict with established national and international frequency services [6]. Down conversion from a higher frequency carrier is one possibility, but it adds complexity to ENDS designed to operate without a receiver.

Visible light links offer an attractive alternative for high-accuracy clock distribution and synchronization over limited areas. Unlike RF, spectrum licensing is not an issue for VLC, and transmitting and receiving optics and electronics can be highly compact. Optical front-ends are also inherently immune to RF electromagnetic interference, and the spatial confinement of light provides both reduced interference to co-located systems and a measure of PHY security in indoor environments. Receivers with active areas on the order of ~ 0.1 mm and upwards are many orders of magnitude larger than the visible-light wavelength (~ 500 nm), which implies that the received photocurrent is effectively an aperture-averaged quantity. As a result, small-scale fading due to phase interference is negligible and modest platform motion does not induce deep fades, as would be in coherent RF links.

A fundamental difference between radio links and most practical optical links is the detection modality. VLC systems employ intensity modulation with direct detection, in which the receiver senses optical power rather than the amplitude of the electromagnetic field [7]. Consequently, the received waveform is real-valued and positive. This constrains feasible modulation schemes (e.g., requiring a direct current (DC) bias or unipolar formats).

The usable BW of a VLC link is bounded on both the transmitter and the receiver sides. On the transmitter side, the LED (or laser diode) rise and fall times set the practical modulation BW. Commodity high-brightness LEDs exhibit turn-on and turn-off times on the order of 20 ns [8], supporting signal BW in the tens of megahertz.

On the receiver side, BW is limited by the photodetector and the analog front-end. A positive-intrinsic-negative photodiode [9] paired with transimpedance amplifier can offer BW comparable to the transmitter, allowing tens of megahertz operation with suitable noise performance.

Alternatively, a photovoltaic (PV) cell can be used as a receiver [10]. In this case, the BW is limited mainly due to the high internal capacitance of the PV cell [11]. The power consumption of the receiver amplifier must be considered in a low-power device. Generally, a high BW amplifier implies high power consumption. The low BW of PV cells reduces the BW requirements of the amplifier and allows the use of low-power-consuming parts.

2.3 Low-power symbol-synchronous communications

Wireless multi-hop communication is an efficient mechanism for extension of network coverage with low expenditure on network infrastructure. This is especially beneficial for widely distributed deployments, e.g., wireless sensor networks or robotic swarms operating in a large-scale area. Most of the multi-hop protocols rely on store-and-forward relay techniques, where nodes repeatedly forward messages to neighboring node according to a collision-free schedule, e.g., in a time division-multiple access manner. Unfortunately, this results in the excessive packet transmission delay, which grows fast with the number of hops. To improve the scalability of wireless multi-hop networks, symbol-synchronous communications [12], [13] were proposed, which deserve special attention due to their suitability to ENDS. In particular, the simplicity of the required radio design combined with the lack of time synchronization between the nodes and low-power opera-

tion makes symbol-synchronous communications a perfect solution for highly distributed ENDs deployments, especially with strict latency constraints.

Figure 2.2: Multi-hop transmission workflow for symbol-synchronous transmission.

Figure 2.2 illustrates the general idea of symbol-synchronous transmission, where each relay node detects and relays the current symbol instantly after receiving a sufficient number of samples, rather than waiting until the entire frame is received, as is done in store-and-forward routing. In a most simple case, the short-pulse-based OOK modulation scheme is applied. To ensure that subsequent symbol transmissions do not interfere with each other, the pulse duration T_p is kept shorter than the symbol period T_s . Each pulse is therefore followed by a silent “guard” period. When symbol 1 is sent, the transceiver transmits a short pulse for duration $T_p \ll T_s$. When symbol 0 is sent, the sender remains silent during the total symbol period T_s . A raised cosine filter is applied to shape the pulse to limit the BW of the baseband signal and mitigate spectrum leakage.

Figure 2.3: Window-based symbol detection.

The symbol-synchronous communications protocol needs a tailored detector to accurately detect the symbol from the received signal, mitigating the interference of redundant copies of the same symbol. Therefore, a window-based detector is used, where observation is limited to a short time slot called the detection window, whose duration is defined by the window length L ($T_p < L < T_s$). The transceiver only listens to the signals and makes decisions during the detection window. Once a symbol (1 or 0) is successfully detected, the transceiver switches from reception to transmission and relays this symbol to the neighboring nodes. The detection window will slide to the next position, exactly one symbol period T_s further (cf., Figure 2.3).

To further reduce the energy consumption of the ENDs, various sleeping techniques can be applied. The simplest one is random sleep/wake-up, where ENDs wake-up to relay each particular symbol with fixed probability p . The lower is this probability, the more energy is saved, but the higher is the chance that the symbol will not reach the destination. The network density is important for the optimal selection of p , as with higher density, less nodes are required for the successful delivery of each symbol. To evaluate the trade-off between the wake-up probability p and the reliability, the experiments in MATLAB were conducted. In these experiments, 25 and 100 nodes were placed in a regular grid in a 25 m² area, and packet error probability is estimated for a 128-bit packet. The preliminary results are shown on Figure 2.4.

Figure 2.4: 128-bit packet error probability for a network deployed in 25 m² area, consisting of (left) 25 nodes; (right) 100 nodes.

Chapter 3

Backscattering communications

This chapter presents an initial assessment of BC as a key enabler for ENDS in future 6G networks. It outlines the main technical challenges associated with enabling reliable communication from ENDS and examines their system-level integration through symbiotic radio architectures that embed ENDS into existing networks. Building on this concept, the chapter further investigates backscatter communication with arbitrary wideband ambient radio signals, focusing on signal modelling and synchronization aspects. Finally, it discusses practical implementation topics, including backscatter modulation techniques, END demodulator hardware design, and joint visible light–backscatter schemes for energy-efficient operation within existing wireless infrastructures.

3.1 Technical challenges

This section highlights the most relevant technical challenges inherent to backscatter systems. The challenges presented have strong implications for the whole design of the system, including the design of the receiver that detects the signals backscattered by an END, the system transmitter’s waveform and BF design, and the hardware design of the END itself.

3.1.1 Weak and heavily interfered signals

The main BC difficulty arises because the END does not generate its own carrier but merely reflects and modulates an incident wave. This means that the useful signal experiences a double path loss (transmitter–END–receiver) and is often several orders of magnitude weaker than the direct link between transmitter and receiver. The receiver must therefore detect a signal that is simultaneously close to or below the thermal noise floor and heavily overshadowed by a much stronger component, creating severe dynamic range requirements.

These power imbalances in wideband backscatter channels were quantified in [14], while [15] showed that in distributed multiple-input multiple-output (MIMO) backscatter, the direct path dominates so strongly that it masks the echo unless specific BF and generalized likelihood ratio test detection schemes are used. Early work on ultrawideband BC addressed this through correlation-based receivers and clutter cancellation [16], but in practice the weak-signal and strong-interference problems must be handled jointly.

3.1.2 Synchronization of the END with the infrastructure

Synchronization between the END and the access points (APs) is critical, since backscatter detection often relies on coherent processing or packet alignment [17]. ENDs typically lack stable oscillators, leading to clock drift and timing jitter that degrade phase coherence and increase symbol error rates. In [18] it was shown how these impairments affect ultrawideband radio frequency identification (RFID) performance, while [19] proposes a system design allowing for system-side synchronization techniques to compensate drift without increasing device complexity. At large scale, synchronization challenges extend to multiple-access: thousands of tags transmitting asynchronously can cause collisions and inter-tag interference, demanding scalable schemes for timing, coding, and channel allocation.

3.1.3 TX BF for initial access

Downlink power is the main bottleneck for passive ENDs, which rely entirely on incident energy for activation and modulation. Due to path loss and fading, the received power may often fall below the wake-up threshold unless energy is spatially focused. This initial access problem is critical not only for WPT but also for BC itself: without sufficient incident energy, the END cannot switch its load or generate a detectable backscatter signal, preventing any communication from being established.

To overcome this, [15] demonstrates distributed MIMO BF for bistatic backscatter, where transmitter-side spatial filtering enhances tag detectability while suppressing the direct link interference (DLI). In parallel, [20] developed a closed-loop WPT scheme with adaptive waveform and BF, where codebook-based BF is used for initial access. In [21], initial access is addressed by employing physically large or distributed antenna arrays. By leveraging environment reflections and adjusting beam phases, the method expands initial access range and reduces fading margins compared to simple beam sweeping strategies. This enhances the likelihood of waking up passive ENDs when CSI is unavailable.

3.1.4 Nonlinearities in the reflection coefficient of the END

ENDs employing BC modulate information by varying their antenna reflection coefficients. This reflection coefficient is not ideal because the integrated circuit (IC) input impedance depends on both frequency and the instantaneous voltage across the chip terminals during EH. This introduces nonlinear behavior: the effective modulation depth varies with input power, and harmonics or intermodulation products may be generated. In [22] it was shown that backscatter contains both antenna-mode and load-modulated components, where the latter depends strongly on the nonlinear tag impedance. In [23] these effects were experimentally measured, showing that IC impedance changes with input power and alters the backscattered signal. This behavior can be formalized by modeling reflection as frequency-dependent, nonlinear, and time-varying, linking it to positioning and sensing errors [24]. More recently, [25] incorporated such nonlinearities into the design of amplitude-shift keying reflection states, optimizing them under practical sensitivity and error-rate constraints.

3.2 Modulation techniques and their effect on low-power 6G network protocols

Choosing the proper modulation technique requires taming trade-offs tailored to the specific use case. The modulation impacts the MAC behavior on many fronts while also determining tag power consumption. Designing low-power solutions implies resorting to low-complexity hardware, making modulation technique designs a fragile balance between functionality/range and power consumption. This is all while not sacrificing important aspects such as security and reliability.

In long-range backscattering, three BC modulation families dominate, each with different complexity, spectral behavior, and receiver compatibility. These are: i) binary switch-based like OOK/frequency shift keying (FSK) and load modulation, ii) chirp spread spectrum (CSS), and iii) in-phase and quadrature (IQ)/digital modulator architectures. We describe them briefly next.

OOK (as used by R2D, see Section 2.1.2) toggles between (near) matched and strongly mismatched loads to realize on/off symbols; it is simple and ultra-low power, but when backscattering onto *ambient* communication the unknown, modulated carrier complicates demodulation and tends to require carrier-aware receivers [26], [27], [28], [29] or carrier signals normalized in their power level over a defined period of time for carrier-independent demodulation, as further detailed in Section 3.5. **FSK** drives the RF switch at one of multiple tones to translate the incident carrier, enabling frequency-domain separation from the illuminator and easier commodity reception; it is widely used in long-range bistatic links and to shift backscatter out of the incumbent band [30], [31], [32]. Load modulation (small-signal amplitude perturbation) is prevalent in near-field communication (NFC)/short-range systems, but is range-limited [26], [33]. Spectral compliance for binary frequency shifting benefits from harmonic/image suppression techniques and multi-level impedance shaping [34], [35], [36], [37].

Chirp-based schemes adapt long range (LoRa)/CSS for backscatter to exploit processing gain and commodity gateways: (i) *passive-on-LoRa* (e.g., PLoRa) splices or offsets ambient chirps to encode bits while remaining decodable at LoRa receivers [38], [39]; (ii) *blind-chirp* uses dual frequency shifts ($\pm BW/2$) and splicing to form valid chirps [40]; (iii) *chirp-interval modulation* transmits short, shifted “anchor” chirps whose spacing encodes data, improving rate while retaining long range [41]; (iv) *non-linear/curved chirps* (e.g., Prism, CurvingLoRa) reshape chirps to mitigate near-far problems and enable collision resolution and higher concurrency [42], [43]. These approaches increase robustness below 0 dB SNR and can remain compatible with commodity LoRa demodulation, albeit sometimes with custom receivers for best performance [38], [42], [43].

Analog IQ-impedance modulators synthesize continuous backscatter constellation trajectories (amplitude/phase control) with good spectral containment and harmonic suppression [35]. Over-sampled switching emulates analog envelopes with high-rate pulse width modulation (PWM) of the RF switch and benefits from careful spectral shaping [34]. All-digital based modulation (direct memory access (DMA)/direct digital synthesis (DDS)) stores precomputed waveforms (e.g., LoRa chirps) in memory (Figure 3.1) for extreme simplicity. These are transferred from memory to a single general-purpose input/output (GPIO)-pin through DMA which then controls the RF switch. However, square-wave spectra introduce strong harmonics unless multi-throw impedance shaping or filtering is used [44], [45], [46]. These methods unlock flexible waveforms and advanced multiplexing at modest power, at the cost of slightly higher tag complexity [26].

Figure 3.1: DDS stores a waveform in memory which is transferred to a GPIO-pin through DMA.

3.2.1 What the modulation choice implies for low-power 6G protocols

Table 3.1: Overview of modulation techniques and their implications on 6G protocol designs.

Modulation	Sync./wake-up	Access	Conc.	Near-far	Spectral eff.	Security	
OOK	unique sequence	grant-free	carrier cancellation	tag power	bad	MAC	
FSK	unique sequence	query, grant-free	multi-tone	tag power	good	tone-shift, MAC	
CSS	preamble, RSS indicator correlation	RSS (RSSI)	query	multi-tone, symbol-bin, curved chirp	chirp shape	best	MAC

Future low-power 6G will lean on grant-free access, opportunistic/ambient carrier reuse, and energy-aware control. The modulation family chosen at the END level directly shapes feasible MAC/stack behaviors. The following 6 stack properties (summarized in Table 3.1) are most heavily impacted by the choice. A short discussion shows how they are impacted by the different modulation families.

Synchronization and wake-up

Ambient-tag operation hinges on packet detection at nano/microwatt budgets but with a limited range. Their range is limited to 100 m or less [40], [47]. In order to achieve hundreds of meters reception range in bistatic systems the tag is assumed to be close to the transmitter [38], [42], [47], up to a couple of meters or even less. CSS-based schemes exploit LoRa preambles/RSSI patterns or correlators to wake and align with minimal sampling rates [48], [49]; binary OOK on ambient carriers typically demands carrier/state awareness or auxiliary detection logic [27], [30]. Design takeaway: CSS-friendly ambient detection favors *receiver-agnostic wake-ups and precise symbol timing* at tiny power, enabling grant-free, *opportunistic uplinks* when illuminators are present [38], [39].

Access (query-based vs. pure grant-free)

Concurrency at scale benefits from *query/beacon-triggered* backscatter (e.g., symbol-bin or tone-bin assignment), where tags transmit upon a short beacon and use orthogonal cyclic shifts/frequencies [40], [50], [51]. This can be provided by micro-beacons (user equipment (UE), AP, roadside unit) to which tags reply concurrently, followed by an optional 1–2 bit

acknowledgment (ACK)/negative ACK (NACK) being sent back to the tags [40], [50]. This couples naturally with CSS/FSK variants that map tags to fast Fourier transform (FFT) bins [38], [47]. In contrast, pure grant-free OOK/FSK without beacons keeps tags simpler but suffers from a higher collision probability and near-far problem; slotted ALOHA or tone diversity can partially mitigate this [26], [30]. For low-power 6G, beacons, light-touch coordination from *edge anchors* (UEs or roadside units) is attractive when ambient traffic is intermittent [38], [39].

Concurrency and near-far robustness

CSS enables rich *many-to-one* decoders: symbol-bin multiplexing (NetScatter style), frequency-shift multiplexing (Aloha/XORLoRa style), and curved-chirp separation (Prism-style) support tens to hundreds of concurrent tags with modest scheduling [40], [42], [46], [47], [50]. Windowing and reserved guard bins absorb residual timing offsets from low-cost tags. Binary FSK can also scale via multi-tone assignment but requires careful sidelobe control [34]. Protocol consequence: networks can offer *collision-tolerant grant-free* collection rounds with short beacons, amortizing control overhead across many tags [40], [50].

Reliability, rate adaptation, and feedback

CSS demodulators at the tag side (using envelope/derivative detection) enable μW -level downlink awareness—data-rate hints, channel selection, quick ACK/NACK [48], [49] through a standardized tiny control alphabet. This minimizes the downlink semantics to decrease power consumption. Where downlink is infeasible, monostatic/bistatic symmetry allows *blind rate adaptation* from RSSI without decoding [52], [53]. Protocol consequence: low-power 6G links can adopt *ACK-light* reliability (few-bit feedback) or *blind adaptation* to maintain packet error rate targets while keeping tag power budgets in the tens of μW [54], [55]. Tags decoding feedback signals hold the same range limitation as ambient tags. Incorporating energy-aware scheduling through *harvest-then-transmit* and *RSSI-guided rate selection* at tags allows gateways to adapt beacon periodicity to ambient load and tag energy states [52], [54], [56].

Spectrum etiquette and commodity compatibility

Binary OOK and square-wave digital backscatter can leak harmonics; CSS/IQ solutions with multi-level loads suppress images/odd harmonics, easing adjacent-channel protection and enabling coexistence with commodity LoRa wide-area network (LoRaWAN) gateways [34], [35], [38]. This lowers the barrier to *brownfield reuse* of low-power wide-area network infrastructure, which is key to sustainable deployments [39], [43]. Thin software extensions allow multi-tag FFT binning or anchor-chirp detection [38], [42], [43]. Transmitting dedicated tones occupies the existing infrastructure, making it unavailable for active communication. This makes ambient (uplink/downlink) illumination from active nodes preferable and allows reverting to low-duty dedicated tones only when ambient traffic is scarce [31], [38], [39].

Security and addressing

Long-range backscatter without association exposes tracking risks. Lightweight identification via tone/shift bins (binary/FSK) is convenient but linkable; CSS payloads can leverage LoRa(-WAN) security primitives when compatible [39]. Low-power 6G stacks should include *reader*

authentication beacons and *rotating ephemeral identifiers (IDs)* baked into beamed collection rounds, keeping tag logic minimal [33], [57].

3.2.2 Key takeaways

- CSS-based backscatter is the most protocol-friendly for *grant-free, concurrent* collection over long range, thanks to robustness and FFT-domain multiplexing [38], [40], [42], [50].
- Binary FSK offers a sweet spot of simplicity and bin-based scaling, especially for bistatic ambient setups with modest concurrency [30], [32], [47].
- IQ and digital modulators unlock cleaner spectra and agile waveforms, enabling security headers and future 6G features, at slightly higher tag complexity [34], [35], [44].
- Protocols should *co-design* micro-beacons, bin assignment, and minimalist feedback with the chosen modulation to meet ultra-low energy budgets [50], [52].

3.3 Symbiotic radio: integrating BC into current systems

Ambient BC (AmBC) is a symbiotic communication system that reuses the power and spectrum of a primary communication service. For example, the AmBC scheme in [58] leverages the LTE downlink signal. The prototype illustrated in Figure 3.2 demonstrates an AmBC design based on both LTE downlink and uplink cellular systems [59], which is categorized as Topology 4, Catalog Device B in the A-IoT classification framework [60]. In this architecture, backscatter bits ($b=0$ and $b=1$) are encoded by intentionally offset Doppler shifts in the Doppler domain. The artificial Doppler frequencies (dashed triangles) are positioned above the naturally occurring Doppler shifts (solid triangles), thereby enabling the receiver to discriminate the BD signal from ambient interference.

Figure 3.2: An illustration of A-IoT “Catalog Device B” system that exploits the LTE cellular network as an ambient source of information. [61]

In LTE, pilot signals are continuously broadcast in the DL, referred to as cell-specific reference signal (CRS) [62]. The UE performs channel estimation based on these pilot signals transmitted by the BS. This channel estimation procedure, standardized by 3GPP [62], is integrated into the UE baseband processor. A similar mechanism is employed in the uplink (UL), where the corresponding pilot signals are known as sounding reference signal (SRS) [62]. The DL and UL pilot radio elements (REs) are shown in Figure 3.3. These channel estimators detect and track

subtle variations in the electromagnetic environment, while the receiver equalizers compensate for the resulting time-varying channel effects. In practice, the rate of channel estimation significantly exceeds the pace of channel variations. The AmBC exploits this redundancy to embed and convey its own backscatter device (BD) information to fill the gap between practical channel dynamics and the channel estimation rate.

Figure 3.3: Resource blocks of LTE downlink CRS and uplink SRS with single antenna.

In natural wireless propagation, time-varying components are caused by Doppler effect. However, in [58], BD modulated the scattered path by toggling the on and off states in different frequencies, i.e., FSK modulation. The scattered path is recognized as multi-path components from the receiver's perspective. In the delay Doppler signal representation, the scattered path effected by BD illustrates Doppler shift properties, called "artificial Doppler". Those artificial Doppler frequencies are designed to higher than natural Doppler frequencies, as shown in Figure 3.2.

In a sub-GHz LTE system with a center frequency $f_c \sim 800$ MHz,¹ the mobility of surrounding objects are typically assumed not to exceed a maximum velocity v_{\max} of 30 m/s [58]. The resulting Doppler shift f_D is expressed as

$$f_D \leq \frac{v_{\max}}{c} f_c = 80 \text{ Hz}, \quad (3.1)$$

where c denotes the speed of light. Accordingly, the lower bound of the BD signal spectrum is 80 Hz, indicated by solid triangles in Figure 3.2. The upper bound, however, is constrained by the channel estimation rate and the LTE cellular parameters. For instance, in one possible configuration, the DL channel estimation rate can reach up to 4 kHz [60], while the UL channel estimation rate can reach up to 0.5 kHz as proposed in [63]. Based on these configuration, the feasible BW of the BD signal spectrum is approximately 80 Hz to 2 kHz in the DL and 80 Hz to 0.5 kHz in the UL, as Figure 3.2 dashed triangles shown.

¹For example, in LTE band 20, where DL is 806 MHz and UL is 847 MHz.

Figure 3.4: a) Measurement setup. b) Measured vs theoretical AmBC link bit error rate (BER) in LTE uplink and downlink as a function of effective signal-to-noise ratio (SNR).

To evaluate the performance of the proposed system, measurements were conducted to compute BER in both UL and DL directions. The UL is implemented by srsRAN LTE BS and commercial UE. Meanwhile, the DL is implemented by commercial LTE BS and universal software radio peripheral software-defined radio (SDR) UE. The system operated with a 10 MHz BW and carrier frequencies 806 MHz and 847 MHz, in DL and UL, respectively. In these measurements, two UEs were employed. In the UL direction, a commercial off-the-shelf Samsung SM-G9860 phone was used to transmit SRS signals, illuminating a nearby BD and allowing the eNB to receive the reflected signal. In the DL direction, an open-source SDR-based UE implementation [64] was used, which synchronized itself with the BS and estimated the channel based on the CRS transmitted by the eNB. The BD employed FSK modulation, and used two square waves of different periodicities, i.e., 125 Hz and 250 Hz, respectively, with a symbol duration of 40 ms. The measurement setup used for analyzing the link level performance is illustrated in Figure 3.4a. The measured BER at the UE and at the eNB is presented in Figure 3.4b. The x-axis in Figure 3.4b refers to AmBC SNR, instead of LTE SNR.²

3.4 Wideband BC: modelling and synchronization

This section extends the concept of symbiotic radio introduced in Section 3.3 to arbitrary wideband downlink signals. To enable the integration of an END into generic wideband systems, we develop an algorithm that operates on the baseband samples of a wideband ambient system (e.g. the baseband of a WiFi receiver). The aim of the algorithm is to synchronize to the END by estimating the start time of the backscatter modulation and the backscatter link frequency. Additionally, it provides estimates of the CSI involved in the system to allow for a coherent demodulation of the ENDS data.

To develop the algorithm, we first introduce a wide-band signal model to describe the propagation effects inside the backscatter system and the backscatter modulation applied by the END. Next, we resort to the maximum likelihood estimation of the synchronisation parameters and the CSI.

²For detailed SNR metric discussion, please refer to [63].

3.4.1 Baseband-equivalent signal model for ambient BC

Considering the challenges introduced in Section 3.1, a general algebraic model of the signals arising in backscatter systems is required. This model serves as a foundation for the design and development of signal processing algorithms to address the aforementioned challenges in a systematic way. In this section, a basic wideband signal model is presented which captures the linear signal distortions (multipath propagation, linear system response of the BD and the AP) and defines the backscatter modulation as linear operator.

Figure 3.5: System model: A TX sends an OFDM signal, which impinges at the RX as the sum of the strong DLI with several multipath components and the weak backscatter modulated signal from the END.

Let us consider the basic system model depicted in Figure 3.5. We have a wideband system transceiver (TX and RX) forming the AP, and a BD consisting of an antenna and a variable load impedance. At the RX, assuming stationarity of the environment, we can observe the sum of two signals: one static and one varying due to the varying load impedance at the antenna of the BD. From this observation, we can define two signal paths, the DLI and the BC channel. The DLI contains the signal directly coming from the TX, including all its reflections from the environment. Additionally, it contains the structural mode-scattered signal from the antenna of the BD, which is the signal component reflected from BD's antenna independent from its actual load impedance [65].

The antenna mode-scattered signal, on the other hand, is the part of the BD's reflection, which depends on the actual load impedance [65]. Now, if the BD modulates the antenna load impedance, we can assign this signal to the actual BC pinhole channel [66, pp. 477–478], which is the concatenation of the DL and UL channel as shown in Figure 3.5. For the following mathematical considerations, we model all radio channels in the system as complex-valued discrete time finite impulse response filters, representing the sampled baseband equivalent channel impulse responses [66, pp. 106–109]. The finite impulse response captures the propagation effects of the electromagnetic wave in the environment and the linear effects occurring in the hardware (e.g. system transceiver, antennas, cables, and BD).

3.4.1.1 Time domain signal model

The time-domain signal model of the BC system is schematically depicted in Figure 3.6.

A wideband signal $\mathbf{s} \in \mathbb{C}^{\tilde{N}_S \times 1}$ emitted by the transmitter passes through the DL channel $\mathbf{h}_{DL} \in \mathbb{C}^{M_{DL} \times 1}$ to the BD, where $\tilde{N}_S \in \mathbb{N}$ is the dimensionality wideband transmit signal and $M_{DL} \in \mathbb{N}$ is the dimensionality of the DL channel. At the BD, incoming signals are reflected with a time-

Figure 3.6: Schematic overview of the time-domain signal model defined in (3.2).

varying reflection coefficient, representing the modulation with the BC signal \mathbf{b} of dimensionality $\mathcal{D}_{\text{DL}} = \tilde{N}_S + M_{\text{DL}} - 1$. The reflected signal then passes through the UL channel $\mathbf{h}_{\text{UL}} \in \mathbb{C}^{M_{\text{UL}} \times 1}$ to the receiver generating the received backscatter signal \mathbf{y}_{T} , where $M_{\text{UL}} \in \mathbb{N}$ is the dimensionality of the UL channel.

Level differences between the DLI \mathbf{y}_{D} , i.e., the result of \mathbf{s} propagating through the direct link channel $\mathbf{h}_{\text{D}} \in \mathbb{C}^{M_{\text{D}} \times 1}$ (with $M_{\text{D}} \in \mathbb{N}$ being the dimensionality of the direct link channel), and the received BC signal \mathbf{y}_{T} are modelled using the gain factor $g_{\text{T}} \in (0, 1)$ since we assume normalized channel impulse responses (CIRs), i.e. $\|\mathbf{h}_{\text{DL}}\|^2 = \|\mathbf{h}_{\text{UL}}\|^2 = \|\mathbf{h}_{\text{D}}\|^2 = 1$. At the receiver, the DLI \mathbf{y}_{D} is superimposing the BC signal along with circularly symmetric additive white Gaussian noise (AWGN) $\boldsymbol{\nu} \in \mathbb{C}^{\mathcal{D}_{\text{D}} \times 1}$. $\mathcal{D}_{\text{D}} = \tilde{N}_S + M_{\text{D}} - 1$ denotes the length of the received signal. The observable received time domain signal $\mathbf{y} \in \mathbb{C}^{\mathcal{D}_{\text{D}} \times 1}$ is then given as the sum of the backscatter signal, direct link interference and AWGN, resulting in

$$\mathbf{y} = \underbrace{\mathbf{H}_{\text{D}}\mathbf{s}}_{\mathbf{y}_{\text{D}}} + g_{\text{T}} \underbrace{\mathbf{H}_{\text{UL}}\mathbf{B}\mathbf{H}_{\text{DL}}\mathbf{s}}_{\mathbf{y}_{\text{T}}} + \boldsymbol{\nu}, \quad (3.2)$$

where $\mathbf{H}_{\text{DL}} \in \mathbb{C}^{\mathcal{D}_{\text{DL}} \times \tilde{N}_S}$, $\mathbf{H}_{\text{UL}} \in \mathbb{C}^{\mathcal{D}_{\text{D}} \times \mathcal{D}_{\text{DL}}}$ and $\mathbf{H}_{\text{D}} \in \mathbb{C}^{\mathcal{D}_{\text{D}} \times \tilde{N}_S}$ are Toeplitz matrices representing the linear convolutions with the corresponding CIRs \mathbf{h}_{DL} , \mathbf{h}_{UL} and \mathbf{h}_{D} respectively. The BC modulation is modelled by the operator $\mathbf{B} = \text{diag}(\mathbf{b})$. An exemplary backscatter modulation waveform is described in the following subsection. A general overview of other candidate waveforms and their implication on low-power network protocols is given in Section 3.2.

3.4.1.2 Exemplary backscatter modulation signal

BC modulation signals can be modelled using preamble sequences used in current RFID systems for tag-to-reader communication [67]. These signals, in most cases, boil down to periodic³ rectangular pulses, which in turn can be described by PWM signals with 50% duty-cycle, a start time $\eta_b \in \mathbb{N}_0$ and a period of $2T_b$, with $T_b \in \mathbb{N}$, as illustrated in Figure 3.7.

Figure 3.7: Rectangular BC modulation signal with a pulse width of T_b and a start time η_b .

³Periodicity is assumed for the duration of the preamble.

There are two distinct signal states. We assign total absorption to one state (i.e. the case where the load impedance of the antenna of the BD is matched) and nonzero reflection to the other state (i.e. the case where the antenna of the BD is shorted out). The resulting BC modulation signal $\mathbf{b} \in \mathbb{B}^{\mathcal{D}_{DL} \times 1}$ is OOK as shown in Figure 3.7, with $\mathbb{B} = \{0, 1\}$ denoting a binary set.

3.4.1.3 Additional assumptions

For typical indoor scenarios, the coherence BW of the radio channel is large [66, pp. 125–143] compared to the BW of the BC communication, since only low data-rates are used [67]. Therefore, we assume \mathbf{b} to be narrowband compared to the CIRs, in particular $M_{UL} \ll T_b$, so we can approximate the BC signal with

$$\mathbf{y}_T \approx g_T \tilde{\mathbf{B}} \mathbf{H}_{UL} \mathbf{H}_{DL} \mathbf{s} = \tilde{\mathbf{B}} \mathbf{H}_T \mathbf{s} = \tilde{\mathbf{B}} \mathbf{S} \mathbf{h}_T = \tilde{\mathbf{b}} \odot \mathbf{S} \mathbf{h}_T. \quad (3.3)$$

The adjusted BC modulation signal $\tilde{\mathbf{b}} \in \mathbb{B}^{\mathcal{D}_D \times 1}$ is the actual BC modulation signal \mathbf{b} but zero-padded to match the dimensionality of \mathbf{y}_T . The matrix $\tilde{\mathbf{B}} = \text{diag}(\tilde{\mathbf{b}})$ represents the modulation with the adjusted signal. With this approximation, we neglect the transients to the envelope \mathbf{b} caused by \mathbf{h}_{UL} in \mathbf{y}_T . The vector $\mathbf{h}_T \in \mathbb{C}^{M_T \times 1}$ represents the BC CIR obtained by the linear convolution of DL and UL CIR [68]. We construct the linear convolution matrix $\mathbf{S} \in \mathbb{C}^{\mathcal{D}_D \times M_T}$ from \mathbf{s} . We further ensure $M_T = M_{DL} + M_{UL} - 1 \stackrel{!}{=} M_D$ by zero-padding the CIRs accordingly. We assume the transmit signal \mathbf{s} to be known, e.g., by reconstruction from an OFDM transmission over the direct link or by using codebook-based pilot sequences.

3.4.2 Synchronisation and CSI estimation for coherent uplink

Here, we address the problem of estimating the CIRs of a single-input single-output (SISO) BC system as depicted in Figure 3.5 from a given received signal vector \mathbf{y} induced by a known wide-band transmit signal \mathbf{s} . We use the exemplary backscatter waveform introduced in Figure 3.7. The obtained estimates allow for a cancellation of the DLI and for the synchronisation of the END with the AP, which allows for a coherent demodulation of the BC waveform emitted by the END [69, pp. 40–46].

3.4.2.1 Maximum likelihood estimator

Let us consider the likelihood function of \mathbf{y} with the approximation in (3.3). Since we assume AWGN at the receiver, i.e. $\boldsymbol{\nu} \sim \mathcal{CN}(\mathbf{0}, \sigma_\nu^2 \mathbf{I})$, we can treat the time domain received signal \mathbf{y} as a Gaussian random vector with a mean of $\mathbf{y}_D + \mathbf{y}_T$ and a covariance matrix $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_\nu = \sigma_\nu^2 \mathbf{I}$. So we get $\mathbf{y} \sim \mathcal{CN}(\mathbf{y}_D + \mathbf{y}_T, \sigma_\nu^2 \mathbf{I})$ [70]. The resulting likelihood function is

$$p(\mathbf{y}; \mathbf{S}, \mathbf{h}_D, \mathbf{h}_T, \tilde{\mathbf{b}}, \sigma_\nu^2) = \frac{1}{(\pi \sigma_\nu^2)^{\mathcal{D}_D}} \exp \left[-\frac{1}{\sigma_\nu^2} \left\| \mathbf{y} - \mathbf{S} \mathbf{h}_D - \tilde{\mathbf{b}} \odot (\mathbf{S} \mathbf{h}_T) \right\|^2 \right]. \quad (3.4)$$

This can be concentrated with respect to the CIRs \mathbf{h}_D and \mathbf{h}_T , i.e., parameters \mathbf{h}_D and \mathbf{h}_T can be eliminated and expressed as a function of the BC modulation signal $\tilde{\mathbf{B}}$. This process yields an objective function which only depends on the modulation signal $\tilde{\mathbf{B}}$. Since $\tilde{\mathbf{B}}$ is a function of the BC modulation parameters, we get an objective function whose maximisation yields $\hat{\eta}_b$ and \hat{T}_b , which also eliminates the DLI as \mathbf{h}_D is eliminated. The obtained BC modulation parameters $\hat{\eta}_b$ and \hat{T}_b can be reinserted in reverse order to first obtain $\hat{\mathbf{h}}_D$ and to lastly obtain $\hat{\mathbf{h}}_T$.

First, the likelihood function defined in (3.4) is maximized with respect to the impulse response of the BC channel \mathbf{h}_T while keeping the other parameters fixed. So we get

$$\hat{\mathbf{h}}_T(\tilde{\mathbf{B}}, \mathbf{h}_D) = \arg \max_{\mathbf{h}_T} \rho(\mathbf{y}; \mathbf{S}, \mathbf{h}_D, \mathbf{h}_T, \tilde{\mathbf{B}}, \sigma_\nu^2) = (\tilde{\mathbf{B}}\mathbf{S})^+ (\mathbf{y} - \mathbf{S}\mathbf{h}_D), \quad (3.5)$$

where $(\cdot)^+$ denotes the pseudoinverse.

Now having the estimate of the BC channel impulse response, we insert $\hat{\mathbf{h}}_T(\tilde{\mathbf{B}}, \mathbf{h}_D)$ into (3.4) and maximize with respect to the direct link channel impulse response \mathbf{h}_D while keeping the remaining parameters fixed. The resulting estimate reads

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{\mathbf{h}}_D(\tilde{\mathbf{B}}) &= \arg \max_{\mathbf{h}_D} \rho(\mathbf{y}; \mathbf{S}, \mathbf{h}_D, \hat{\mathbf{h}}_T(\tilde{\mathbf{B}}, \mathbf{h}_D), \tilde{\mathbf{B}}, \sigma_\nu^2) \\ &= (\mathbf{S} - \tilde{\mathbf{B}}\mathbf{S}(\tilde{\mathbf{B}}\mathbf{S})^+ \mathbf{S})^+ (\mathbf{y} - \tilde{\mathbf{B}}\mathbf{S}(\tilde{\mathbf{B}}\mathbf{S})^+ \mathbf{y}). \end{aligned} \quad (3.6)$$

We exploit the idempotent and Hermitian property of $\tilde{\mathbf{B}}$, so we further simplify (3.6) and obtain

$$\hat{\mathbf{h}}_D(\tilde{\mathbf{B}}) = (\mathbf{S} - \tilde{\mathbf{B}}\mathbf{S})^+ \mathbf{y}. \quad (3.7)$$

Finally, we insert the results of the BC channel estimate $\hat{\mathbf{h}}_T$ from (3.5) and the estimate of the direct link channel $\hat{\mathbf{h}}_D$ from (3.7) into the likelihood function of the received signal and get

$$\begin{aligned} (\hat{\eta}_b, \hat{T}_b) &= \arg \max_{\eta, T} \mathcal{L}(\mathbf{y}; \mathbf{S}, \tilde{\mathbf{B}}(\eta, T), \sigma_\nu^2) \\ &= \arg \min_{\eta, T} \left\| \left(\mathbf{I} - \tilde{\mathbf{A}}(\eta, T)\mathbf{S}(\tilde{\mathbf{A}}(\eta, T)\mathbf{S})^+ - \tilde{\mathbf{B}}(\eta, T)\mathbf{S}(\tilde{\mathbf{B}}(\eta, T)\mathbf{S})^+ \right) \mathbf{y} \right\|^2 \end{aligned} \quad (3.8)$$

where

$$\tilde{\mathbf{A}} = \mathbf{I} - \tilde{\mathbf{B}} \quad (3.9)$$

is the binary complement of the modulation operator $\tilde{\mathbf{B}}$.

3.4.2.2 Simulation results

We evaluate the estimator using a standard-compliant OFDM signal. Sample rate f_s , subcarrier count N_c , and subcarrier spacing of the transmit signal are defined by an IEEE 802.11ax transmission mode operating at $f_c = 2.44$ GHz with 80 MHz BW. The BS modulation signal is based on an FM0 Extended Preamble defined in the electronic product code Class 1 Gen 2 RFID standard [67], which corresponds to a 40 kHz and 50% duty-cycle PWM signal with a total duration of 300 μ s. The dimensionality of the transmit signal \mathbf{s} and the received signal \mathbf{y} are set such that it matches the duration of the BS modulation preamble with the given sample period. The received signal \mathbf{y} is synthesized using the signal model in (3.2) without the approximation in (3.3).

We employ Monte Carlo simulations for different combinations of interference-to-noise ratios (INRs) (i.e. the SNR of the normalized OFDM signal) and signal-to-interference ratios (SIRs),

$$\text{INR} = 10 \log \frac{1}{N_c \sigma_\nu^2}, \quad (3.10)$$

$$\text{SIR} = 20 \log g_T. \quad (3.11)$$

For each experiment, the BS modulation start time η_b is drawn from a discrete uniform distribution $\mathcal{U}(0, T_b)$ and the CIRs are randomly generated. To characterize the performance of the estimator of the BS modulation parameters in (3.8), we define the rate of correct estimation in (3.12), where $e_\eta = \eta_b - \hat{\eta}_b$, $e_f = f - \hat{f}$ with $f = f_s/2T_b$, $\Delta_\eta = 100$ and $\Delta_f = 1$ kHz define the spacing of the grid. By

$$R_c = \mathbb{P}[|e_\eta| < \Delta_\eta \cap |e_f| < \Delta_f], \quad (3.12)$$

we denote the probability that the start time and frequency of the BS modulation signal are correctly estimated with grid-spacing accuracy.

Figure 3.8 shows the simulated results for R_c , where we can see at first glance that for the given setup, the SNR of the BS signal $\text{SNR}_{y_T} = \text{INR} + \text{SIR}$ needs to be above -20 dB such that the estimation in (3.8) performs reliably for the given simulation parameters.

Figure 3.8: Rate of correct estimation of BS modulation parameters for different combinations of INR and SIR using the estimator in (3.8).

3.5 Envelope detector behaviour on modulated WiFi signals

Backscatter communication enables ultra-low-power devices to transmit data by modulating existing RF signals coming from a transmit device or from the environment. This eliminates the need for active RF generation on the device side, significantly reducing power consumption and enabling battery-free operation. However, the effectiveness of such systems hinges on the ability of the receiver to reliably demodulate the received modulated signal, particularly when the excitation waveform deviates from a simple continuous wave (CW) tone to more complex waveforms such as OFDM and DSSS. These waveforms are currently used in WiFi and are considered to be candidate waveforms for future 6G systems.

Traditional RFID demodulators are typically optimized for CW excitation, where the signal envelope remains constant over time. In such cases, envelope detection using a diode (or transistors in diode configuration [71]) followed by a low-pass filter is sufficient to extract the modulated information. However, when the excitation signal exhibits significant envelope variation, as is the case with OFDM and DSSS, the demodulator must contend with rapid amplitude fluctuations that can degrade detection performance.

OFDM signals, for instance, are composed of multiple orthogonal subcarriers. The superposition of these subcarriers results in a composite waveform with high PAPR, leading to sharp peaks and

deep fades in the signal envelope. These fluctuations can challenge the rectification behavior, especially if the signal amplitude falls below the envelope threshold for significant portions of the symbol duration. In contrast, DSSS signals spread the data across a wider BW using a pseudo-random chip sequence. While the envelope of a DSSS signal is more stable than that of OFDM, the high chip rate introduces rapid transitions that can impact the envelope detector.

To investigate these effects, a series of experiments were conducted using CW, OFDM, and DSSS waveforms transmitted at 2.45 GHz with a SDR. Each waveform was configured with a 50% duty cycle and a symbol or chip duration of $2\ \mu\text{s}$, resulting in a periodic structure with a $4\ \mu\text{s}$ cycle. The receiver as part of a test IC in complementary metal oxide semiconductor (CMOS) technology, employed a standard envelope detector followed by a comparator with a fixed threshold [72].

Figure 3.9: Measured envelope detector output for CW, OFDM, and DSSS signals. Although the signal envelopes differ, the output pulse widths remain statistically similar when the energy per interval is constant. The black dashed line indicates the target pulse width of $2\ \mu\text{s}$, while the pink reference lines represent the expected output based on the IC's analog behavioral model at minimum sensitivity. As RF input power decreases, the ON pulse width shortens, and detection ceases once the sensitivity threshold is reached: $-17.36\ \text{dBm}$ for OFDM, $-16.5\ \text{dBm}$ for DSSS, and $-16.3\ \text{dBm}$ for CW. This demonstrates that the signal type has only a minor influence on overall demodulator behavior.

The transmitted waveforms were further designed to have low energy deviations over short time intervals. The OFDM waveform with a symbol duration of $4\ \mu\text{s}$ has normalized power in this time interval, as well as the DSSS with a symbol duration of $1\ \mu\text{s}$. This specific waveform design targets further uniform demodulator behaviour by keeping the transitions from high to low amplitude low and the energy level uniform.

The results in Figure 3.9 confirm that the demodulator output is largely consistent across waveform types when the energy per interval is held constant. For each RF input level, the traces for CW, OFDM, and DSSS indicate the minimum and maximum pulse widths measured over multiple pulses. The statistical variation is negligible for most power levels and only becomes noticeable for DSSS near the sensitivity limit. At low input powers, the ON pulse width decreases and eventually falls below the detection threshold, which occurs at $-17.36\ \text{dBm}$ for OFDM, $-16.5\ \text{dBm}$ for DSSS, and $-16.3\ \text{dBm}$ for CW. While OFDM shows the largest deviation close to this threshold, all waveforms converge toward the target width of $2\ \mu\text{s}$ as power increases.

At higher input levels, a slight overshoot of the target width is observed for all signal types, but this effect is minor compared to the variations near the threshold. These findings confirm that the RC-based temporal averaging and waveform alignment effectively mitigate envelope fluctuations, ensuring that the demodulation process is robust and does not produce incorrect pulse widths for any waveform type under constant energy conditions [73], [74].

3.6 Joint VLC-BC for proximity-based indoor asset tracking

In Section 2.2, the potential of using VLC signals for device synchronization is discussed. In addition, VLC can be integrated into BC systems for more applications, such as indoor positioning and asset tracking. Herein, we introduce a joint VLC-BC system for indoor asset tracking purposes. We propose to use a BD attached to an asset for harvesting energy and receiving identifiers from LED, which are then used to modulate and reflect ambient RF carrier waves to report its proximity within specific VLC cells, thereby localizing and tracking the BD.

Figure 3.10: System model of joint VLC-BC for indoor asset tracking.

We consider a BD attached to a moving asset (e.g., a robot or mobile platform) in an indoor environment, as illustrated in Figure 3.10. The objective is to localize or track the asset by tracking the BD. In this indoor scenario, LED lamps are typically installed on the ceiling, each illuminating a specific coverage area on the ground. Consequently, the entire space is divided into multiple sub-areas. Each LED transmits a VLC signal containing a unique ID, modulated into normal white light using techniques such as Bias-tee or LED drivers. The BD is equipped with a photodetector or solar cell that performs PV conversion and demodulates the received VLC signal, extracting the LED-ID. This ID is used to control backscatter modulation. The PV-converted signal modulates the incidence RF carrier signal transmitted by an ambient RF source. The modulated RF signals are backscattered and can be received by standard RF receivers.

The proposed system is validated with a bistatic backscatter radio setup in an indoor office for a PoC, shown in Figure 3.11. The setup is composed of two LED modules marked with LED-1 and LED-2, a BD [75], [76], a 2.4 GHz ambient RF signal generator connected to an omni-directional

dipole antenna, and a spectrum analyzer connected to another omni-directional dipole antenna. An arbitrary waveform generator sends continuous binary FSK-modulated sequence '010101...' to the driver (Bias tee) of each LED module and adopt intensity modulation. LED-1 adopts frequencies of $f(1, 1) = 8$ kHz and $f(1, 2) = 9$ kHz, representing bit '0' and bit '1', respectively. LED-2 adopts frequencies of $f(2, 1) = 10$ kHz and $f(2, 2) = 11$ kHz, representing bit '0' and bit '1', respectively. The intensity-modulated light is then emitted. The BD receives various light intensities depending on its position with respect to the two LED modules. The BD is moved between the two tripods aligning the track marked on the ground, with a 1.6 m distance in 0.1 m steps. The backscatter received signal strength (RSS) is recorded by the spectrum analyzer at all BD's positions, shown in Figure 3.11. The BD modulates the incidence 2.4 GHz RF carrier signal with the PV-converted light signal. The modulated RF signal is received by the spectrum analyzer, shown in Figure 3.12 for three different BD positions, 0.4 m, 0.8 m, and 1.2 m, respectively.

Figure 3.11: A PoC setup.

Figure 3.12 (left) shows the spectrogram measured when BD is at the position of 0.4 m of the track, which is exactly below LED-1. Other than the carrier frequency component $f_c = 2.4$ GHz, the received backscattered signal predominantly contains the subcarrier components of ± 8 kHz and ± 9 kHz, indicating that the VLC signal sent from LED-1 is received, modulated, and backscattered by the BD. Figure 3.12 (middle) shows the spectrogram measured when BD is at the position of 0.8 m of the track, which is below the midpoint of two LEDs. Other than the carrier frequency component, the received backscattered signal contains the subcarrier components of ± 8 kHz, ± 9 kHz, ± 10 kHz, and ± 11 kHz, indicating that the VLC signal sent from both LED-1 and LED-2 is received, modulated, and backscattered by the BD. Figure 3.12 (right) shows the spectrogram measured when BD is at the position of 1.2 m of the track, which is exactly below LED-2. Other than the carrier frequency component, the received backscattered signal predominantly contains the subcarrier components of ± 10 kHz and ± 11 kHz, indicating that the VLC signal sent from LED-2 is received, modulated, and backscattered by the BD.

Figure 3.12: Spectrogram of the received backscattered signals, when BD is positioned at 0.4 m, 0.8 m, and 1.2 m, from left to right.

Figure 3.13 shows the backscatter RSS measurement results and the corresponding illuminance level at the BD. The RSS measurement is repeated 5 times. The illuminance level is measured by a commercial off-the-shelf lux meter. For BC signal including the ID of LED-1 (blue solid line), its RSS varies with the position of the BD with respect to LED-1. The RSS increases when the BD approaches LED-1 and decreases when the BD moves away. A similar trend can also be observed for the BS signal, including the ID of LED-2 (blue dashed line), where its RSS increases when the BD approaches LED-2 and decreases when the BD moves away. Moreover, when the BD moves below the midpoint of two LED modules, RSS of both BS signals converge to approximately -79 dBm. In conclusion, experimental results indicate that the BD can be localized or tracked in an indoor area where multiple LEDs are deployed, using a combination of VLC and BC. With appropriate LED deployment, seamless positioning of the BD is achievable. The study of 2D/3D LED deployments is planned for D3.2 and D3.3.

Figure 3.13: Measured RSS of the backscattered signal and illuminance at the BD for different positions.

Chapter 4

RF charging protocols & optimization

The design of efficient RF WPT systems requires an integrated understanding of waveform generation, antenna deployment, synchronization, and protocol operation. Energy transfer efficiency depends not only on PHY parameters such as power conversion efficiency (PCE), path loss, and antenna configuration, but also on the degree of available side information—ranging from full CSI to CSI-free scenarios. Similarly, synchronization accuracy (in time, frequency, and phase) directly determines the achievable BF gain and spatial selectivity of the power delivery.

This chapter focuses on the optimization of RF charging protocols under realistic infrastructure and hardware constraints. Section 4.1 introduces a taxonomy of system capabilities, categorizing WPT operation by available information and synchronization precision. Section 4.2 reviews CSI-free initial access and wake-up strategies, including rotary, randomized, and sense-then-charge (STC) methods. Section 4.3 presents experimental insights from the Tectile testbed, quantifying how infrastructure synchronization and calibration influence achievable WPT performance. Section 4.4 analyzes the impact of waveform design on PCE and wake-up efficiency, while Section 4.5 summarizes low-complexity and scalable protocol architectures. Finally, Section 4.6 illustrates a real-world use case involving energy-optimized powering of electronic shelf labels (ESLs) in a retail environment.

4.1 Available system information and capabilities

The performance and optimization potential of RF-WPT systems depend strongly on the information available at the infrastructure and the achievable synchronization capabilities. In this section, we outline the different levels of information granularity and synchronization assumptions. These will serve as a reference framework throughout the subsequent sections when comparing protocols, measurements, and design choices.

By systematically categorizing WPT systems according to the type of information available (CSI-based, location-based, or CSI-free) and the achievable synchronization (time, phase, frequency), we establish a taxonomy that will be used throughout this section. This taxonomy enables a clear comparison of protocol design choices under realistic system constraints.

4.1.1 Antenna deployment

Single-antenna systems are simple, low-cost, and do not rely on spatial processing, but their energy efficiency and coverage control are fundamentally limited. When multiple antennas are available at the energy transmitter (ET), BF, diversity, and spatial multiplexing strategies become possible. The achievable gain depends on the type and quality of side information at the transmitter. Multi-antenna systems can be deployed in several configurations:

- **Co-located (Massive MIMO):** Antennas are concentrated in a compact array at a single BS or ET. This setup enables highly coherent BF and spatial multiplexing, assuming sufficient CSI, but the coverage footprint is limited by geometry and path loss.
- **Distributed MIMO:** Antennas are geographically distributed across multiple APs or nodes. This configuration provides macro-diversity, improved coverage, and spatially selective power delivery, but requires more stringent synchronization and backhaul coordination.
- **Large Arrays (Near-Field Operation):** When arrays scale to extreme dimensions, the spherical nature of wavefronts must be accounted for. Near-field BF enables energy focusing at specific locations in space rather than angular directions, unlocking new opportunities for highly selective and efficient WPT, but also introducing challenges in modelling, calibration, and protocol design.

4.1.2 Available system information

CSI-based approaches

Historical CSI: The transmitter uses outdated channel information, which may result in mismatched BF weights and degraded efficiency.

Partial CSI: Only partial channel knowledge (e.g., large-scale fading, path loss, or statistical channel properties) is available. Optimization strategies can exploit this but remain suboptimal compared to full CSI.

Full CSI: The transmitter has perfect knowledge of instantaneous channel coefficients, enabling optimal precoding and maximum BF gains.

Location-based approaches

Location Known: The positions of the ENDS are available, allowing geometry-based precoding and beam steering.

Area Known: Only the area or region where ENDS are located is known, which enables spatially targeted energy delivery but not fine-grained BF.

CSI-free approaches

In some cases, no channel or location information is available. The transmitter must rely on blind or randomized strategies (e.g., sweeping, phase randomization, or broadcast-like schemes) until feedback from the ENDS becomes available.

4.1.3 Synchronization capabilities

Synchronization plays a central role in enabling coherent combining and minimizing destructive interference in multi-antenna WPT. We distinguish three aspects of synchronization, each of which can be assumed to be ideal or impaired.

Time synchronization

Time synchronization determines the temporal alignment of the transmitted signals across all ETs within a distributed WPT infrastructure. In the ideal case, all transmitters are precisely aligned in time with negligible jitter, ensuring that the emitted waveforms overlap coherently at the energy receivers (ERs). Perfect alignment maximizes constructive interference and guarantees efficient power combination at the receiver.

In the impaired case, residual timing offsets remain between transmitters due to propagation delay, clock drift, or jitter in the synchronization network. These imperfections reduce the effectiveness of coherent combining and can introduce inter-symbol or inter-slot interference, particularly when the offsets approach a significant fraction of the carrier period or modulation symbol duration. Even small deviations may cause destructive superposition of the radiated fields, lowering the effective received power.

Phase synchronization

Phase synchronization ensures that the carrier phases of all transmitters remain aligned over time. Under ideal conditions, perfect phase coherence across antennas allows the transmitted waves to combine constructively at the intended focus point, enabling efficient BF and energy concentration. Such alignment requires accurate calibration of the entire transmit chain, including RF oscillator, cable, and antenna phase responses.

When phase synchronization is impaired, random or drifting phase offsets develop between transmitters. These offsets reduce the coherent gain of the array and can lead to partial signal cancellation in certain spatial regions. The resulting fluctuations degrade both instantaneous power delivery and long-term fairness among ENs. In practice, limited phase coherence can be tolerated in WPT, but beyond moderate drift, BF performance deteriorates rapidly.

Frequency Synchronization

Frequency synchronization refers to the alignment of the carrier frequencies among distributed transmitters. In the ideal situation, all nodes share a common frequency reference, often derived from a shared 10 MHz local oscillator or network-distributed clock. This eliminates carrier frequency offsets and maintains long-term phase stability, allowing consistent coherent operation.

Under impaired conditions, small frequency mismatches accumulate over time, causing gradual phase rotation between transmitters. Without correction, these drifts disrupt constructive interference and require periodic re-synchronization or compensation mechanisms. Frequency offsets therefore represent a slow but persistent source of coherence loss, especially in large or distributed WPT systems where independent oscillators operate over extended durations.

4.2 CSI-free initial access & wake-up

Initially, ENDS are fully depleted and cannot transmit pilots or backscatter signals. Consequently, no CSI or location information is available, and the infrastructure must rely on CSI-free charging protocols. These protocols aim to deliver sufficient initial energy for wake-up, enabling subsequent coherent operation. This section reviews several CSI-free approaches.

4.2.1 Rotary and randomized methods

Early studies on blind WPT strategies have proposed *rotary* and *randomized-phase* excitation methods to distribute energy without prior CSI. In the rotary approach [77], a mechanically or electronically steered antenna continuously rotates its beam pattern across azimuth and elevation angles. Each END intermittently receives a short burst of focused power as the beam sweeps past its location. This ensures fairness and predictable coverage in small deployments but results in low average efficiency when only few devices are active.

Randomized-phase schemes [78] generalize this idea to distributed arrays. Each transmitter applies an independent, time-varying phase to its carrier, producing stochastic constructive interference at random spatial locations. Over time, every END experiences peaks in instantaneous power, allowing eventual energy accumulation without coordination or feedback. Experiments show that such methods yield diversity-like gains of several decibels compared to static single-antenna beacons.

While both rotary and randomized methods are attractive for their simplicity and scalability, they exhibit inherent trade-offs:

- **Scalability:** Randomized methods scale to large arrays without mechanical components and can serve many ENDS concurrently.
- **Efficiency:** The average transmit power is spread over the entire coverage area, resulting in lower per-device efficiency when only a few ENDS are present.
- **Latency:** Charging relies on random power peaks; therefore, the time-to-wake-up can range from seconds to minutes depending on the transmit power and rectifier sensitivity.

Randomized-phase or rotary illumination is well suited for network bootstrapping, activating the first set of devices that can then assist in establishing synchronization or pilot feedback.

4.2.2 Sense-then-charge

A more structured CSI-free strategy is the STC protocol proposed in [79]. It partitions each transmission frame into two stages: *sensing* and *charging*. During the sensing period, ENDS use ultra-low-power detectors to measure incident energy and estimate whether they are within range. Devices that detect sufficient power remain active for the subsequent charging period, while others revert to sleep to conserve energy.

The STC protocol thus provides a self-regulating mechanism that adapts charging effort to the network state. By dynamically adjusting the sensing time allocation ratio γ , the system can balance responsiveness (short wake-up delay) against fairness (serving more distant devices). Figure 4.1 illustrates the performance tradeoffs in the sense-then-charge protocol as a function

Figure 4.1: (a) Average minimum received power (P_k) (top) and (b) average error (bottom) over L transmission blocks as a function of sensing allocation ratio (γ) for the number of devices $K = 2$ (left) and $K = 4$ (right). We assume 24 receive antennas, 12 transmit antennas, and 10 dB transmit power. The STC approach is compared with perfect knowledge (PK), rotary antenna BF (RAB), and all antennas sending independent signals (AA-IS). The average error is shown for angles of arrival (θ), reflection coefficients (α), and the estimated line-of-sight channel relying on sensing parameters.

of the sensing allocation ratio γ . Increasing γ improves sensing accuracy by enabling more reliable estimation of the devices' locations; however, this comes at the cost of shorter charging duration and thus a reduction in the minimum received power. Notably, there exists an optimal γ for each scenario that yields sufficiently low estimation error while still maintaining strong power delivery. At this operating point, e.g., $\gamma \approx 0.1$ for $K = 2$, the STC protocol consistently outperforms the benchmark schemes and, in some cases, approaches the ideal performance achieved under perfect knowledge, demonstrating its ability to adaptively balance energy transfer efficiency and sensing precision. To obtain the best γ , a simple line search can be performed by applying the STC mechanism for each γ value, and picking the best one.

From a protocol design perspective, STC can be viewed as an intermediate step between fully blind charging and fully coordinated operation. It requires no explicit feedback but leverages local sensing to improve efficiency. The main advantages are:

- **Reduced waste:** Charging energy is focused on active devices only.
- **Scalable operation:** All ENDS follow the same low-complexity rule set without central scheduling.
- **Graceful degradation:** Performance gradually decreases under heavy load rather than collapsing abruptly.

However, the periodic sensing intervals introduce small overheads, and the accuracy of the energy detector limits performance when input power is near the sensitivity threshold.

4.2.3 Single- vs multi-tone initialization

Recent experimental campaigns on the Tectile testbed [80] have shown that waveform selection strongly affects initial wake-up efficiency. In the absence of CSI, transmitters typically use a simple waveform—either single-tone or multi-tone—to energize the environment uniformly.

Continuous-wave single-tone excitation yields the highest rectifier PCE, enabling ENDs to reach their activation threshold (0.3 V to 0.5 V) quickly. Measurements show that under typical transmit powers, ENDs can harvest enough energy to backscatter a short pilot within tens of seconds. This makes single-tone excitation ideal for the initial charging stage. In contrast, multi-tone (multisine) signals provide smoother harvested DC levels but lower efficiency at the same average transmit power. Many ENDs fail to reach the wake-up threshold within the one-hour measurement window, especially in low-power regimes.

The findings suggest a hybrid initialization strategy:

- Use single-tone excitation during the bootstrap phase to ensure deterministic wake-up.
- Once a subset of ENDs can transmit pilots, switch to coherent WPT modes (e.g., beam-focusing or retrodirective).
- Incorporate scheduling and backoff mechanisms to handle the stochastic nature of wake-up delays across devices.

In practical deployments, wake-up times on the order of tens of seconds are expected. Proper slot allocation and adaptive retry policies can thus prevent contention during the transition from CSI-free to coordinated operation.

4.3 Performance impact by the infrastructure capability

The efficiency and spatial selectivity of RF WPT depend strongly on the synchronization accuracy, calibration quality, and array configuration of the transmitting infrastructure. To quantify these dependencies, a detailed measurement campaign was conducted in the Tectile testbed [81], [82].

The experiments employed a 31-element distributed antenna array operating at 920 MHz, representative of an indoor WPT deployment such as a warehouse or retail aisle. Each antenna tile incorporates an independent transmit chain but shares precise timing and frequency references through the following synchronization backbone: i) a 1 PPS (pulse-per-second) reference distributed to all transmitters, ensuring sub-1 μ s time alignment; ii) a common 10 MHz local oscillator providing frequency coherence across nodes; and iii) periodic reciprocity calibration to remove static phase offsets between uplink and downlink paths, allowing phase-coherent beamfocusing. This configuration represents the expected synchronization features of future distributed WPT infrastructures interconnected over Ethernet or optical fiber. The testbed allows controlled transitions from non-coherent to fully coherent operation, supporting detailed evaluation of performance versus capability.

Four transmission strategies were evaluated:

1. **SISO:** A single antenna active, serving as baseline reference with no combining gain.
2. **RPS (Random-Phase Sweeping):** All transmitters radiate at a common frequency but

with random, periodically changing phases to emulate non-coherent diversity.

3. **BF (Beamfocusing)**: Fully coherent operation using reciprocity-based phase alignment to focus energy on a target point.
4. **G-BF (Gaussian Beamfocusing)**: Same as BF but with deliberate Gaussian phase perturbations of standard deviation σ_φ , emulating imperfect synchronization.

Table 4.1: Overview of WPT strategies, main effects, and synchronization requirements.

Strategy	Applied TX Phase	Main Observations	Time	Freq.	Phase
BF	$-\hat{\varphi}$	Highest median received power; tight focal spot $\approx \lambda/2$; ~ 14 dB gain vs. RPS; deep off-target suppression (< -90 dBm).	✓	✓	✓
G-BF	$-\hat{\varphi} + \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_\varphi^2)$	Smooth degradation with phase noise: < 1 dB loss for $\sigma_\varphi \leq 20^\circ$, ≈ 3 dB loss beyond 40° ; near-BF efficiency under relaxed calibration.	✓	✓	±
RPS	$\varphi \sim \mathcal{U}(0, 2\pi)$	Non-coherent diversity; ~ 7 dB median gain vs. strongest SISO; favourable short-term power peaks; broader illumination footprint.	✓	✓	×
SISO	N.A.	Baseline coverage; no array gain; low efficiency but simplest hardware and zero coordination.	×	×	×

The comparative measurements on Techtile yielded three principal results linking infrastructure quality to charging performance as discussed next.

1) Coherent BF unlocks large efficiency gains. With full-time, frequency, and phase coherence, reciprocity-based BF produced median received power improvements of approximately 14 dB compared to random-phase sweeping (RPS). This gain aligns closely with the theoretical array gain for $M = 31$ equal-power elements. The resulting near-field power distribution formed a tight focal region of diameter $\approx \lambda/2$, enabling precise spatial energy confinement and high efficiency. Outside the focal area, received power dropped below -90 dB, confirming strong suppression of undesired exposure.

2) Phase errors up to 20° incur negligible penalties. By injecting zero-mean Gaussian phase perturbations with standard deviation σ_φ , the study quantified the tolerance of WPT to synchronization imperfections. The results demonstrated < 1 dB median loss for $\sigma_\varphi \leq 20^\circ$ and > 3 dB degradation only beyond 40° . This highlights that WPT systems can maintain near-optimal efficiency under coarser phase control than typically required for high-rate communications. Consequently, calibration and CSI update intervals can be significantly relaxed without notable efficiency loss.

3) Randomized-phase sweeping remains valuable without CSI. When no synchronization or feedback was available, RPS provided a robust baseline by exploiting non-coherent transmit

diversity. The periodic phase changes create stochastic constructive interference peaks, temporarily raising received power above the harvester's activation threshold. Although the average efficiency is lower than BF, the 7 dB median gain over SISO makes RPS particularly effective for powering cold-start devices or for fallback operation when CSI is unavailable.

4.4 Waveform choice on RF WPT efficiency

RF EH is a critical enabler for AmBC systems. The ability to extract sufficient power from RF signals determines the feasibility of battery-free operation. This section highlights how waveform selection interacts with infrastructure capabilities and practical rectifier behavior. First, multi-carrier and single-carrier waveforms are investigated for multi-antenna WPT in the 920 MHz industrial, scientific and medical (ISM) band. Then, we assess the impact of CW, OFDM and DSSS on the PCE in the 2.45 GHz ISM band. Both measurements indicate that average power dominates harvester performance. This is in contrast to state-of-the-art, where the same average RF power, high-PAPR signals achieve better performance.

4.4.1 Large-array excitation: single- vs multi-tone waveforms

A central challenge in RF-WPT is the initial access problem: how to charge fully depleted ENDS when they cannot provide CSI or feedback. Before an END can transmit a pilot, it must harvest enough energy to power its microcontroller unit (MCU) or backscatter circuit. Waveform design is therefore critical during this bootstrap phase.

To investigate this, an experimental campaign was performed on the Tectile testbed [81], [82]. The setup consisted of 31 ceiling-mounted distributed antennas operating at 920 MHz, powering custom RF-harvesters placed at random aisle positions. More details can be found in [80]. Devices were exposed to two excitation strategies:

1. **Adaptive single-tone excitation:** Continuous-wave transmission at one carrier frequency, with varying phase to induce time-dependent constructive interference at random positions (RPS).
2. **Multi-tone excitation:** Superposition of equally spaced tones.

Experimental observations

- **Efficiency:** Single-tone consistently achieved higher RF-to-DC conversion efficiency at the rectifier input. Measured harvested power at identical transmit levels was up to 20–30% higher than with multi-tone signals.
- **Wake-up probability:** Only single-tone reliably enabled devices to cross the MCU threshold voltage (0.3 V to 0.5 V) at low transmit powers. In contrast, multi-tone signals often left devices below this level, preventing pilot transmission.
- **Response time:** With single-tone, devices typically accumulated sufficient energy to backscatter a 10-byte pilot within tens of seconds. Under multi-tone excitation, response times frequently exceeded the one-hour measurement window, making them impractical for initial access (Table 4.2).

- **Stability:** Multi-tone excitation produced smoother DC levels but at a lower average value, which may be insufficient to overcome leakage currents and threshold voltages in most harvesters.

Table 4.2: 50th (P50) and 95th percentile (P95) of the END response time derived from single- and multi-tone measurements for different total transmit powers. Configurations with response times exceeding 1 h are indicated by “—”.

Total transmit power [dBm]	28.34	29.20	30.06	30.92	31.78	32.64	33.44	34.24	35.04	35.84	36.64
Single-tone P50 [s]	—	—	—	620	156	148	76	55	31	20	17
Single-tone P95 [s]	—	—	—	1537	483	410	438	221	125	78	58
Multi-tone P50 [s]	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	55	31
Multi-tone P95 [s]	—	—	—	—	—	—	288	132	69	74	43

Protocol-level implications

These findings translate into several design rules for large-array WPT protocols:

- **Initialization strategy:** Initial charging phases should use single-tone excitation to maximize rectifier efficiency and ensure predictable wake-up at low transmit powers.
- **Transition to steady-state:** Once ENDS transmit a pilot, the system can switch to more advanced strategies (e.g., reciprocity-based coherent BF).
- **Scheduling/backoff:** Because wake-up times span tens of seconds, protocols must incorporate retry and backoff schemes to manage pilot collection without excessive latency.
- **Hardware-protocol co-design:** Improvements in MCU leakage power or lower wake-up thresholds can reduce access delays as effectively as waveform optimization.

4.4.2 Rectifier response to WiFi-band waveforms

An eight-stage differential charge-pump IC implemented in 40 nm CMOS technology was used for further analysis to compare the EH capabilities on different excitation waveforms [72]. This rectifier architecture incorporates gate and bulk biasing techniques to reduce the effective threshold voltage of the transistors [83].

The experimental setup, depicted in Figure 4.2, includes a signal generator based on a SDR platform, a directional coupler together with a spectrum analyser (SA) to verify the transmitted power for each waveform. The signal is then transmitted with a standard WiFi antenna tuned for the ISM band. The device under test (DUT) is the charge-pump IC, which receives the signal through a differential antenna interface.

To assess the impact of waveform characteristics on EH, the PCE of the rectifier was compared under CW, OFDM, and DSSS excitation. Each waveform was normalized to the same average input power to ensure a fair comparison. The spectral properties of the signals are summarized as follows: CW occupies a narrow 1 MHz band, OFDM spans 20 MHz (IEEE 802.11g), and DSSS covers 22 MHz (IEEE 802.11b), as further illustrated in Figure 4.3.

Figure 4.2: Setup for PCE evaluation of the mentioned charge pump, denoted as DUT, using waveform types generated by the SDR. The spectrum analyzer is used to verify the power spectral density (PSD) of the generated signal.

Figure 4.3: PSD comparison for CW, OFDM, and DSSS signals in the 2.45 GHz ISM band.

While theoretical models suggest that high-PAPR waveforms such as OFDM may enhance rectifier efficiency due to the nonlinear response of the diode [84], the analysis indicates that the practical impact of waveform type is minimal. As shown in Figure 4.4, the PCE curves for all three waveforms are nearly identical, with variations below 3% across the tested power range.¹

These findings underscore the importance of average power delivery over instantaneous power peaks. The temporal averaging inherent in the charge-pump architecture effectively smooths out the envelope variations, making the system robust to different waveform types. Furthermore, the biasing techniques implemented in this test IC [72], which enable low forward voltage and high PCE, reduce the impact of high-PAPR waveforms [85], [86].

Protocol-level implications

From a design perspective, this result simplifies the development of EH systems for ambient environments. A single rectifier topology can be employed across a range of signal types without the need for waveform-specific tuning. Future research may explore whether advanced rectifier designs, such as those employing adaptive matching or synchronous rectification, can extract additional benefits from waveform-specific features, particularly in dynamic or multi-source environments.

¹The apparent discrepancy between the conclusions in Section 4.4.1 and the present discussion arises from the fact that the single-tone transmission in Section 4.4.1 corresponds to a CW signal per transmit antenna, where each antenna operates at a different frequency. Moreover, the phase of each CW signal is periodically varied, resulting in a received waveform that is not strictly CW but rather exhibits slow amplitude variations, similar in structure to an OFDM signal with low carrier spacing. Consequently, this setup does not fully correspond to the single-tone versus multi-tone comparison analysed in this section (Section 4.4.2).

Figure 4.4: PCE versus input power for CW, OFDM, and DSSS using the eight-stage charge-pump IC.

4.5 Low-complexity protocols

Scalable RF WPT networks must balance energy efficiency with implementation feasibility. While fully synchronized and feedback-rich architectures can achieve optimal performance, they are often impractical for large-scale or cost-sensitive deployments. This section reviews recent approaches that reduce computational, hardware, and signaling complexity while maintaining acceptable charging efficiency.

4.5.1 Deployment optimization

A first dimension of complexity reduction concerns the placement and geometry of the transmitting infrastructure. Optimizing antenna deployment can substantially improve coverage and power uniformity without requiring real-time coordination.

A worst-case geometric design for transmitter placement was proposed in [87], formulating the problem to minimize the maximum distance-dependent loss across the service area. Building on this, [88] introduced clustering-based deployment, grouping ENDs into spatial clusters to simplify resource allocation and reduce the required transmit power. Heuristic methods further extend this concept. In [89], a lightweight algorithm jointly optimizes antenna position, orientation, and inter-element spacing using only device location estimates, achieving near-optimal coverage with drastically reduced computation. Finally, radio-stripe architectures [90], where antennas are distributed along linear or polygonal cable paths, enable scalable WPT with minimal interconnect complexity. Their simple wiring and repeatable structure make them suitable for near-field operation and cost-constrained deployments such as industrial aisles or corridors.

4.5.2 Simplified transceivers

Low-complexity operation also depends on the efficiency of the transceiver circuitry. To this end, simplified RF-EH models have been developed to guide energy-optimal transmission. The circuit model in [91] minimizes ET power consumption while maintaining sufficient PCE, supporting time-division charging as a computationally efficient alternative to concurrent multi-device oper-

ation. At the PHY, BF can be simplified through maximum ratio transmission (MRT) strategies. [92] proposed a low-complexity MRT precoder that focuses power along the strongest channels, while [93] extended this to per-device MRT, balancing fairness through a lightweight linear programming formulation. Moreover, low-cost hardware such as reflective intelligent surface (RIS) and digital metasurface antennas has emerged as a promising means to reduce hardware complexity. Studies in [94], [95] demonstrate that BF can be realized through simple phase control of surface elements, avoiding the need for fully digital RF chains and providing significant cost and energy savings.

4.5.3 Limited-feedback and distributed BF

Reducing feedback overhead is another major driver of practical scalability. In [20], closed-loop precoding and waveform co-design were implemented using a predefined codebook, enabling efficient beam selection with minimal signaling. Alternatively, distributed BF schemes exploit feedback-free or quantized adaptation. In [96], a retrodirective BF method was presented, where each transmitter automatically aligns its phase based on the energy of received backscatter signals. [97] further reduced overhead by introducing a one-bit feedback mechanism, where transmitters iteratively adjust their power in response to binary energy indicators from receivers. Finally, [98] proposed machine-learning-driven optimization frameworks capable of approximating optimal precoder selection and power allocation in complex environments. Such data-driven methods can adapt to dynamic scenarios with limited computation and signaling, paving the way for scalable, self-optimizing WPT systems.

4.6 Use case: ESL aisles

In this use case, detailed in [99], the optimization of RF WPT for batteryless ESLs in a supermarket aisle is investigated (Figure 4.5a and Figure 4.5b). Each ESL requires only intermittent bursts of energy—roughly 500 mJ per screen update, twice per day—rather than continuous power delivery. This intermittent demand allows for protocol-level optimization of energy transmission, where the objective is to minimize the total system transmit power while guaranteeing that all ESLs receive sufficient energy over the specified time window.

Findings. The study compared two transmission strategies:

- **Non-coherent WPT (unsynchronized ETs):** Antennas transmit independently without phase alignment. The optimization favors spatial sparsity, consistently selecting a limited subset of antennas (about 10) regardless of the total number available. Increasing the number of available antennas beyond this limit does not improve performance. Power allocation remains constant over time slots.
- **Coherent WPT (phase-synchronized ETs):** Full synchronization enables BF and temporal scheduling. In this case, all antennas are exploited, but only a subset of time slots is used. The optimization favors temporal sparsity, reducing oversupply and aligning energy delivery precisely with ESL requirements. With more antennas, the required transmit power decreases, the variance in harvested energy across ESLs is reduced, and overshoot is minimized.

Figure 4.5: Electronic shelf label use case. Several ETs transmit signals over M antennas to K ERs to charge them over N time slots. In the example, illustrated in 4.5b, during slot n only ER_k is targeted, while at $n + 1$ ER_0 and ER_{K-1} are being charged.

Experimental validation with the Techtile testbed (84 ceiling-mounted antennas powering 240 ESLs) confirmed the numerical findings: coherent systems achieve finer energy control and lower total transmit power, while non-coherent setups plateau quickly.

Protocol-level implications. The results imply clear protocol-level design guidelines for RF-WPT in dense ESL deployments:

- **Energy-Aware Scheduling:** ESLs should not be powered continuously. Instead, protocol-level time-slot scheduling can be used to deliver exactly the required energy for each update cycle, reducing overhead energy consumption.
- **Synchronization Trade-offs:** While coherent operation significantly reduces transmit power and ensures fairness, it requires synchronization, calibration, and CSI. This introduces protocol overhead and hardware constraints. In contrast, non-coherent schemes are simpler to implement but less energy-efficient and inherently limited in scalability.
- **Resource Allocation Strategy:** Non-coherent systems benefit from sparse spatial activation (antenna selection), whereas coherent systems rely on sparse temporal activation (slot selection). Protocols should incorporate corresponding mechanisms for antenna clustering or time-slot scheduling depending on system synchronization capabilities.
- **Energy Fairness vs. Efficiency:** Coherent protocols inherently provide more uniform energy delivery across all ESLs, reducing variance and preventing overcharging.

Chapter 5

Energy-aware and lightweight MAC/RRC

This chapter focuses on energy-aware MAC and RRC for ENDS and supporting frameworks. We start motivating security and privacy MAC mechanisms for ENDS. Then, we present our work towards a hybrid channel access strategy, which blends different types of channel access mechanisms depending on the traffic patterns and energy availability. This is followed by discussions on energy-adaptive task scheduling strategies and the parameterizable feedback loop concept. The focus then shifts to energy-aware duty-cycling and wake-up END scheduling mechanisms to maximize information retrieved per event, and a MAC layer design for minimization of the age of information. Finally, we conclude with initial results of a realistic simulation of the 3GPP Rel. 19 A-IoT network in outdoor and indoor scenarios to support further studies.

5.1 MAC layer privacy

When communicating with multiple devices, ENDS can reduce monitoring costs and signaling overhead associated with R2D transmissions, receptions, and processing by employing broadcast-type transmissions, where information intended for multiple devices is grouped into a single transmission. For example, in A-IoT, R2D transmissions, such as paging or Msg2 (the response from the reader after the device's D2R transmission), are typically broadcast in nature [3], [100]. However, such broadcast transmissions can pose security risks, as both camped and non-camped devices may be able to monitor, decode, and read information intended for other devices. This is especially relevant for 3GPP A-IoT Rel.19 compliant devices, as they may not be connected in a secure RRC state with the reader. Consequently, information transmitted over the radio access network (RAN) may remain unsecured. While the core network (CN) can apply security to communications traversing the RAN, information originating from the RAN side itself often lacks protection. Therefore, for future ENDS, it is important to incorporate security and privacy mechanisms at the MAC layer. This ensures that typical R2D transmissions—especially those broadcast in nature—do not expose the targeted device's information (such as MAC control elements or unprotected data) to unauthorized devices.

One major advantage of applying security and privacy mechanisms at the MAC layer is that they can be dynamically adapted based on instantaneous RAN conditions and requirements—factors that the CN is typically unaware of. This adaptability is particularly important in the context of ENDS, where such conditions are more pronounced and sensitive compared to traditional broadband use cases. This is because legacy cellular standards provide more secured bearers

for routing critical information. Additionally, the information routed over control channels is allocated in a dedicated manner and is scrambled using the user's Access Stratum identity, e.g., the C-RNTI. Such mechanisms do not exist in the A-IoT radio access technology.

5.2 Hybrid channel access

At the MAC layer, cellular networks traditionally use a grant-based network access scheme, where devices transmit a schedule request to obtain a grant for scheduled uplink communication, allowing devices to access the channel in a reliable and collision-free manner. Broadband consumer devices transmit this request using dedicated resource blocks in the uplink control channel. However, for low-power and low-complexity IoT devices, which rely on the NB-IoT technology, the uplink control channel does not exist, and a schedule request is sent using the shared random access (RA) channel. More specifically, NB-IoT devices choose a RA preamble and transmit it over the RA channel. Since multiple devices can transmit preambles simultaneously, the BS is responsible for resolving the contention. When multiple devices select the same preamble, a collision occurs. All devices involved in the collision will enter a random back-off and re-attempt the RA procedure. This procedure has been shown to be inefficient in various scenarios due to poor scalability, high control and signaling overhead, and a high number of preamble repetitions [101]. To reduce signaling overhead and access delay, grant-free schemes have been proposed [102]. During grant-free access, each device randomly chooses resource blocks and transmits its packets to BS without waiting for a transmission grant. However, the number of collisions still remains very high, requiring many retransmissions of data packets. The usage of non-orthogonal access can potentially address this issue, but it significantly increases the receiver complexity and is currently not considered by 3GPP for the upcoming 6G specifications.

For ENDS, the problem of retransmissions and high overhead is especially crucial, as they are energy-constrained and rely on unstable energy sources. Hence, the adoption of the fast uplink grant (FUG) concept [103], in which the BS proactively assigns uplink resources to ENDS based on predicted traffic patterns, is very promising. Accurately predicting which ENDS have data to transmit is a challenge and can result in higher latencies (in case of false negatives) or wasted resources (in case of false positives). Existing research on FUG has mainly focused on the latency-reducing aspect. In [104], a probabilistic multi-armed bandit is proposed to optimize the allocation of resources through device activity prediction. In [105], a solution combining FUG and non-orthogonal multiple access is proposed, wherein devices are clustered based on their channel state to ensure effective packet decoding. In [106], [107], [108], traffic prediction FUG frameworks specifically designed for massive IoT scenarios based on On-Off Markov process, Hidden Markov models, and ML techniques, respectively, are proposed.

The energy saving aspect of channel access mechanisms, which is especially useful for ENDS (cf., Figure 5.1), has been less studied. In [109], a preliminary study on the use of FUG techniques for ENDS is performed, and a framework exploiting WPT to enable more easily predictable duty cycles is developed. This study, however, is limited to preliminary numerical results, does not consider other forms of EH, and does not consider other channel access methods. In [110], a first attempt for evaluation of the three uplink channel access methods is made. The evaluation relies on a combination of analytical methods, link-level simulations, and simplified system-level simulations. The evaluation results presented in the paper show the benefits of FUG in energy efficiency, especially for more predictable traffic.

Figure 5.1: Representative channel resource allocation example in ENDs setup.

For the evaluation of different channel access mechanisms in large-scale scenarios, a realistic simulation is needed that has implementations of NB-IoT protocol stack, as well as models of wireless narrow-band channel, energy consumption, batteries, super-capacitors, and energy harvesters. Since none of the existing simulators have all these components, an NB-IoT branch of ns-3 simulator has been extended with additional models for accurate energy consumption and EH (cf., Figure 5.2).¹

The results of the simulations will be presented in next deliverables. The initial experiments will be based on the scenario from [110], but more complex scenarios with mixed traffic and AI-based algorithms for prediction of device activity and energy availability will also be considered.

5.3 Parameterizable energy-aware feedback loops

ENDs operate under the principle that the energy scavenged from the environment equals or exceeds the energy consumed over time. Sources such as solar, vibration, or thermal gradients may be able to supply sufficient energy, yet their availability is highly variable and often unpredictable. This variability requires mechanisms that continuously adjust the workload of the device to match the current and expected energy conditions. Traditional static task scheduling, in which tasks are executed regardless of the energy context, risks depleting energy storage and reducing device lifespan. Instead, feedback loops that consider the energy balance are

¹Check it out here <https://github.com/tudo-cni/ns3-lena-nb>.

Figure 5.2: Extension of ns-3 NB-IoT implementation to support energy consumption and EH modeling.

essential. Such loops allow devices to adapt dynamically by scaling back or reordering tasks when energy is scarce and exploiting surplus energy when available. Importantly, these loops must be parametrizable, enabling configuration for different application goals, such as longevity, responsiveness, or data fidelity.

5.3.1 Energy balance

A prerequisite for such feedback loops is the ability to measure the system’s energy balance: the amount of harvested energy, the current state of charge of the storage, and the energy consumption of individual tasks. Figure 5.3 illustrates this principle. Environmental energy sources, such as solar or RF, are harvested through one or more pumps and managed by the EH manager. The harvested energy can be routed directly to the load when a stable source is available (e.g., strong solar input), or stored in an energy storage device for later use. The storage medium can be chosen according to the use case: capacitors for fast charge/discharge, hybrid capacitors for moderate buffering, or batteries for long-term storage.

The load, consisting of an MCU, peripherals and any additional power circuitry, is typically supplied from the storage device². A PWR_GOOD signal ensures that the load only becomes active when the storage voltage reaches predefined thresholds. To capture the system’s energy balance, two power meters are included: one measuring the input into the storage device, and another monitoring the load consumption. In scenarios where the load is directly powered from the storage, both meters are required to correctly map current consumption and harvested power. However, when the node primarily operates from the storage under intermittent or ultra-low EH (e.g., RF), a single meter at the storage suffices.

²Power management units such as the Analog Devices LTC3105 [111] recommend this approach. Other units, however, provide regulated on-chip power outputs, e.g., e-peas AEM20940 [112], specifically for application loads. These outputs are typically limited to low-power applications and are often insufficient to sustain higher-power wireless links, such as NB-IoT. On the AEM20940, this is limited to 80 mA.

Power metering can be achieved via Coulomb counting, where the instantaneous current is continuously integrated over time (such as Analog Devices LTC2959). While this method provides high accuracy, it becomes challenging in systems where energy is frequently depleted or rapidly fluctuating due to unreliable or intermittent energy scavenging. In practice, when the energy storage element is a capacitor, monitoring its voltage is often sufficient, since the stored energy is approximately linearly related to voltage for small voltage ranges. When the storage is a non-linear device, such as a battery or a hybrid capacitor, the relationship between voltage and stored energy is more complex, and additional calibration or modeling is required to accurately estimate the energy state. In these cases, combining periodic voltage measurements with occasional current integration can provide a practical compromise.

Figure 5.3: Energy balance in an END. The EH manager collects energy from environmental sources (e.g., solar, RF), regulates it, and either forwards it directly to the load or stores it in an intermediate energy storage device (capacitor, hybrid capacitor, or battery). The load (MCU and peripherals) is powered from the storage and enabled via a PWR_GOOD signal when voltage thresholds are met. Power meters are placed at both the input to the energy storage and the load to monitor harvesting and consumption.

5.3.2 Energy-adaptive task scheduling

Several adaptive strategies can be used, individually or in combination, to ensure that energy consumption does not exceed availability, hence supporting sustainable END operation. These strategies enable the device to continue to function even under fluctuating energy conditions while optimizing the quality-of-service (QoS).

Duty Cycle Regulation One common approach is to regulate the duty cycle of tasks according to the available energy [113]. This involves adjusting the frequency or duration of task execution to match the current or predicted energy availability. For example, in an END that periodically sends environmental sensor updates, the system may reduce the update rate during periods of low energy input, conserving power while still providing essential monitoring. In contrast, when the energy input is high, the update rate can be increased to provide more real-time data. This concept is often referred to as *energy budget-based duty cycling* [114], [115]. A related approach, *predicted harvesting-based duty cycling*, goes a step further by estimating the energy that will

be harvested in the near future and proactively adjusting the execution of the task accordingly. For example, a solar-powered water quality sensor may predict high insolation during midday and temporarily increase its sampling rate to capture more detailed measurements, while reducing updates at night or during cloudy periods [116], [117].

Task Prioritization Another method involves prioritizing tasks according to their importance. High-priority tasks continue to execute even under energy scarcity, while lower-priority tasks are deferred until energy conditions improve. For example, a flood detection sensor can prioritize sending immediate alerts to a remote server over routine temperature recording when the device's energy reserve is low. This ensures that critical functions remain operational, while noncritical functions are temporarily postponed [118].

Task Adaptation In addition to adjusting timing, the nature of tasks themselves can be modified to reduce energy consumption while still achieving essential objectives. For sensing, this may involve switching to simpler, lower-power measurement methods that provide reduced quality of information but consume significantly less energy. For example, detecting stagnant water could rely on a basic resistive sensor rather than a high-resolution camera, which would capture a richer dataset, but at a substantially higher energy cost. Similarly, communication can be adapted to balance energy use and QoS. Low-power protocols such as LoRaWAN allow data transmission at a reduced energy cost compared to cellular standards like NB-IoT, albeit at lower data rates and higher latency. By selecting the communication protocol dynamically, an END can maintain connectivity even when energy is limited [119].

Modern energy-neutral systems often combine the above strategies in a single adaptive scheduler. Techniques range from simple rule-based adjustments [120] to predictive models leveraging historical EH patterns [121] and even ML models that optimize task scheduling in real time [122].

A promising direction for future research lies in the design of parameterizable feedback loops, which explicitly link the monitored energy balance to task scheduling strategies. Rather than applying generic adaptations such as duty cycling or task prioritization in isolation, the key challenge is to parameterize these adaptations according to the requirements of the specific use case. This raises the question of how EH dynamics influence overall system performance — not only in terms of energy autonomy, but also with respect to QoS, latency, reliability, and the functional scope of the application.

In the context of IoT, this means explicitly capturing application priorities as configurable parameters. For example, a smart agriculture deployment could parameterize the minimum sensing frequency required to prevent crop stress, while allowing higher-resolution sampling during periods of energy surplus. Similarly, in structural health monitoring, vibration sensing could be degraded to low-frequency threshold checks under constrained energy conditions, while switching to high-resolution waveform capture when energy availability permits.

Exploring such parameterizations can benefit from methods that go beyond case-specific implementations. One possible approach is to develop flexible evaluation frameworks — for example, simulation environments — that allow observation of how energy-aware scheduling affects application-level performance.

5.4 Energy-aware duty-cycling schedules

END networks must balance application tasks with strict energy budgets. A practical setting comprises a BS serving many ENDS that rely solely on harvested energy to sense and report alarms/events. The central objective is to manage duty cycling and on-demand wake-ups so that relevant information per event is maximized while device batteries remain sustainable over long horizons. A wake-up radio (WuR) enables addressable activation of sleeping ENDS, limiting main-radio use to when communication is actually needed.

Efficient network coordination is essential given A-IoT constraints and event-driven traffic patterns [123], [124]. As A-IoT deployments must increasingly support stricter performance requirements, recent efforts have shifted from static duty-cycling schedules to adaptive coordination strategies that incorporate contextual information, traffic variability, and energy availability [124], [125]. Solutions using fixed thresholds or traffic prediction are proposed in [126], but fall short in dynamic or large-scale deployments. To overcome these limitations, spatial correlations and ML have been considered to guide device scheduling. For instance, clustering-based scheduling can improve scalability by enabling localized coordination and prioritizing device wake-ups in dense environments, thereby reducing redundant sensing and improving coverage efficiency, as demonstrated in [124], [127], [128]. These techniques are often complemented by ultra-low-power WuRs, allowing asynchronous waking up of idle nodes and on-demand data acquisition with minimal energy overhead [129]. Meanwhile, model-free ML techniques have gained traction for managing sleep–wake transitions under uncertain EH and traffic conditions. Indeed, RL agents often outperform static policies by adapting to real-time changes in device state and environmental inputs [125], [130]. More recently, transformer-based architectures, with their powerful sequential modeling and policy optimization capabilities, have become appealing for edge environments [131]. These methods integrate long-term temporal dependencies and context-awareness into activation policies. Still, considerable effort is required to achieve scalable, energy-efficient, and dependable coordination in dense, distributed A-IoT networks. We contribute here by introducing an energy-aware method to maximize the useful information collected and transmitted about a sensing event in such challenging scenarios.

5.4.1 Use-case: system setup

Consider the coverage area of a BS that serves as the gateway for a set \mathcal{N} of N ENDS as depicted in Figure 5.4. Moreover, the time is slotted into transmission time intervals (TTIs) with duration τ . We assume that the coordinator is aware of the position of each IoT device (IoT D) and that the epicenter of each event follows a two-dimensional uniform random distribution. Events occur independently in each TTI with probability α .

Each END operates in four states: *idle* (listening for events), *active* (event detected), *transmission* (reporting via the main radio), and *sleep* (WuR only). Events occur randomly over the area; their influence on an END decays with distance and determines the potential information that the END can contribute. The BS aggregates the information reported across triggered ENDS using application-dependent functions (e.g., maximum, or an aggregation to model saturation/redundancy), reflecting how multiple, spatially correlated observations combine [124]. The BS may issue wake-up signals to ENDS in sleep when additional information is valuable (e.g., nearby ENDS with high energy availability). Transition probabilities among the four states depend on event incidence, duty-cycle parameters, battery sufficiency, and spatial

Figure 5.4: IoT network in which the BS collects information from various ENDs that depend on EH to remain operational. The impact of an event on the surrounding ENDs is represented through a probability activation function that decreases with distance from the event's epicenter to the ENDs. The BSs may selectively wake up certain ENDs, hoping to obtain more information about the detected event [132].

correlation (used to estimate the likelihood that a neighbor also observes the event). This yields a Markovian description of END operation under BS control, where END energy consumption is state-dependent (transmit, idle sensing, WuR listening).

5.4.2 Optimization framework

The long-term goal is to *maximize average information per event* subject to the implicit energy sustainability constraint. Because exact dynamic optimization is intractable for large networks, three complementary strategies are considered: (i) heuristic duty-cycle tuning; (ii) spatial K-nearest neighbor (KNN) clustering with round-robin sensing and targeted wake-ups; and (iii) data-driven control via RL and decision transformers (DT).

Heuristic + spatial KNN: tunes duty-cycle parameters by exhaustive search to hit a deployment-dependent target information level. A stronger spatial method builds KNN/Voronoi structures from END positions, forms clusters sized by sensing reach, and enforces round-robin sensing within each cluster so that exactly one END is active per TTI while others sleep on WuR. When an event is detected, the BS selectively wakes additional, highly correlated neighbors until a preset information target is achieved, minimizing redundant activations and conserving energy.

RL: the BS sets binary per-END duty-cycle actions to save energy without increasing misdetections. The reward balances network idleness (energy saving) against missed events. In the *post-detection* stage, the BS decides which sleepers to wake to maximize event information while penalizing excessive activations.

DT: to reduce online exploration, offline sequence modeling is used: trajectories of {state, action, reward} over recent episodes are embedded and passed through a self-attention stack. The DT outputs per-END actions by attending to episodes that produced high rewards under similar conditions, effectively learning the policy.

5.4.3 Results

We consider normalized energy parameters, *i.e.*, transmission consumes 10 units, idle state consumes 1 unit, while the WuR consumes 1/14 units, the battery has a maximum capacity of 100 units. EH rates are independent for each END; 250 Monte Carlo runs span 10^4 TTIs and multiple spatial deployments. A genie-aided upper bound is included (the closest END always detects the event if within 5 meters range). In this model, the information received is represented by a non-increasing function $p(d_{i,j}) \rightarrow (0, 1]$, which indicates a diminishing influence of the i^{th} event as the distance to the j^{th} END, $d_{i,j}$, increases. Consequently, the information received is $\max_j(p(d_{i,j}))$. In this case, we used the function $p(d_{i,j}) = \exp(-d_{i,j})$.

Figure 5.5: (top left) Mean information received by the BS per event; (top right) mean energy consumption per END per TTI in units; and (bottom) percentage of missed events as a function of the number of ENDs. [132].

The proposed energy-aware control scheme delivers substantially more information per event at lower or comparable energy consumption. As density increases, RL approaches the genie bound in terms of information detection, while KNN and tuned duty cycling also achieve considerable gains. Additionally, mean energy per END per TTI also decreases with the proposed methods while misdetections fall below 0.01%, as shown in Figure 5.5.

In general, employing schemes such as Voronoi, KNN, and RL, for partitioning coverage and serializing sensing can be beneficial. Additionally, incorporating WuR for addressable, on-demand

activation can enhance awareness of energy consumption and EH. This allows for the joint configuration of duty cycles, ensuring a positive net energy balance. Together, these strategies improve availability, reduce detection latency and missed detections, and extend the lifespan of the system while adhering to EH constraints.

5.5 MAC protocols to minimize Aol

The age of information (Aol) quantifies information freshness by measuring the time elapsed since the most recent update from a device was received. As more cyber-physical systems that require fresh information are proposed and implemented [133], the interest in the Aol metric increases. In those systems, updates are time-stamped, and the knowledge of both their content and when they were measured or generated is required for proper operation. Typically, the average Aol and peak Aol are considered as network-level performance metrics, and the performance can be directly optimized, for example, by prioritizing transmissions at the MAC layer from devices with the highest Aol. Within cyber-physical systems, the objective of reducing Aol must be balanced with the constraint of device energy consumption [134]. Although transmitting constant updates is an effective method for lowering Aol, such a strategy is not energy efficient. For ENDs, managing power consumption must be prioritized alongside Aol.

We consider a network with N ENDs transmitting over an erasure channel, with the erasure parameter inversely proportional to the transmit power. We present two protocols for transmission based on the devices' battery levels. In the partially-aware protocol, devices know when their battery levels surpass a given threshold δ , and use the transmit power corresponding to this battery level. In the fully-aware protocol, the devices have perfect knowledge of their battery levels, and select the transmit power based on this knowledge. A baseline is also considered, with devices unaware of their battery levels, attempting transmissions with fixed transmit power, with their batteries possibly being depleted before the transmission is finished.

We consider unitary energy arrivals and devices with a battery capacity of 10 units. Moreover, packets are generated with probability p and are stored in the ENDs' buffers until they decide to transmit them with probability proportional to the battery level in the case of the full-aware protocol and on the energy threshold for the partially-aware protocol. In Figure 5.6, we evaluate the performance when varying the energy arrival rate.

The performance of the partially-aware protocol is highly dependent on the packet generation probability. When packets are rarely generated (lower p), this approach achieves its minimum average Aol with a threshold of $\delta = 10$, performing similarly to the fully-aware strategy. Conversely, when packets are more frequent (larger p), the partially-aware protocol can outperform the fully-aware one, provided that its threshold is properly tuned to the system parameters. Tuning this threshold, however, may not be feasible in some implementations, as it might necessitate a feedback link from the BS to the ENDs, adding to the system's complexity. Lastly, the baseline typically performs worse than both energy-aware approaches. When energy arrivals are relatively infrequent, its oblivious transmission policy results in numerous failed attempts, even though there are instances where the devices possess sufficient energy for a successful update. It is worth noting that under a regime with more frequent energy arrivals, this behavior could be incidentally beneficial, as allowing some ENDs to deplete their batteries might reduce network congestion and thereby enable successful transmissions for other ENDs.

Figure 5.6: The average Aol as a function of the energy arrival rate in the setup considered.

5.6 Realistic simulation of A-LoT

In 3GPP Rel.18, initial work was carried out to define deployment scenarios and traffic models for A-LoT, leading to the identification of simplified protocol requirements. Rel.19 formalized these concepts through the specification of Device 1, characterized by passive uplink transmission and envelope-based downlink reception, eliminating the need for traditional RRC procedures. Specifically, TR 38.848 [61] outlines use cases and topologies where MAC and RRC functions are minimized or removed in order to reduce energy consumption and complexity. Additionally, TR 38.769 [4] specifies, among other things, PHY factors such as waveform design and access mechanisms, which influence MAC behavior.

At the MAC layer, 3GPP proposes slotted-ALOHA and contention-free access schemes. These are designed to support typical A-LoT applications (e.g. rapid inventory and command operations) with minimal coordination [135]. Slotted-ALOHA consists of dividing time into slots, and each device attempts transmission at the beginning of one without prior coordination. Slotted-ALOHA is considered for scenarios where devices transmit randomly and do not require strict latency or reliability values. In such scenarios, the communication can be triggered by environmental (temperature threshold, presence detection, ambient light level changes), contextual (proximity to other devices, energy availability), or network-specific (updating, synchronization) events. On the other hand, in contention-free access schemes, resources are pre-allocated by the network. Contention-free access schemes are considered for scenarios where higher reliability and lower latency are needed, or where traffic patterns can be predicted. However, these schemes introduce additional complexity and signalling requirements, making it less efficient for scenarios where data transmissions are infrequent or difficult to predict. RRC functionality is either absent or replaced by lightweight control signalling, allowing devices to operate without maintaining a persistent connection state and therefore reducing energy consumption.

This section introduces the first steps to develop a network simulator in MATLAB for evaluating different MAC/RRC strategies in realistic environments. 3D maps and geospatial models are utilized to compute multipath channel propagation in realistic indoor and outdoor environments,

thereby enhancing simulation fidelity. Different atmospheric impairments are simulated, affecting the computed channel models. Ray tracing algorithms applied to the 3D scenarios imported in MATLAB are used to model the propagation paths that reflect, refract, and diffract through the environment between BSs or A-IoT readers and A-IoT devices, enabling the signal propagation modelling in complex scenarios to predict radio coverage and channel behaviour.

The resulting propagation paths based on the physical characteristics of the environment are used to calculate channel impulse responses and path characteristics, which can later be fed to the network simulator. This allows us to assess how different protocol strategies perform in terms of data rate, latency, energy efficiency, and reliability, depending on the deployment scenario. This approach ensures that A-IoT protocols are simulated in environments that closely model real-world deployments.

Outdoor scenarios are modelled using data extracted from OpenStreetMap or 3D models designed using Blender. This open-source database provides detailed information on buildings and street geometries, which are essential to accurately model signal propagation. On the other hand, indoor scenarios are designed using Blender tool. The data obtained from OpenStreetMap and the 3D models generated in Blender are imported into MATLAB to be used as 3D environment models that serve as the basis for channel simulation. In total, four different scenarios defined as "scenarios of interest" in 3GPP's TR 38.901 [136] are selected to be simulated:

- **urban macro (UMa)**: these scenarios are urban environments with wide, long streets and large buildings. Paseo Castellana (Madrid) is used as an example of UMa in the simulations.
- **urban micro (UMi)**: similarly to UMa, these are urban setting, but denser than the previous ones. They are characterized by narrow, winding streets and irregular, short buildings. Lavapiés neighbourhood (Madrid) is used as an example of UMi in the simulations.
- **rural macro (RMa)**: these scenarios of interest are characterized by combinations of areas with few small buildings irregularly scattered and large rural areas with vegetation. Consuegra municipality (Toledo) is used as an example of RMa in the simulations.
- **Indoor Office**: these scenarios are small, closed locations with corridors, closed or partially-closed rooms and furniture (e.g. chairs, tables, closets or lockers). A generic office model including partially-closed rooms, walls, tables and chairs made of materials like glass, wood, concrete or foam (which directly influence the channel calculations) is used as an example of indoor office in the simulations.

Table 5.1 and Figure 5.7 show details of the scenarios chosen for the simulations.

Table 5.1: Details of simulation scenarios.

Scenario of interest	Real scenario	Size	BS height	BS output power
UMa	Paseo Castellana	1 km x 1 km	~ 100 m	40 dBm
UMi	Lavapiés neighbourhood	500 m x 500 m	~ 20 m	40 dBm
RMa	Consuegra municipality	5 km x 5 km	~ 35 m	40 dBm
Indoor Office	Generic office model	80 m x 30 m	~ 6 m	20 dBm

As a first step, ray tracing algorithms and the channels computed from their results are tested. For this purpose, a single transmitter acting as a BS is placed in the highest point of each

Figure 5.7: Examples of scenarios to be simulated.

geospatial model. The antenna of this transmitter can be customized in terms of topology, number of antenna elements, transmission frequency or output power, among other parameters. For this first test, antennas with one and two horizontally-arranged isotropic elements transmitting at a frequency of 3.5 GHz are used. For the case of two-element antennas, the separation between elements is half the transmitted wavelength. Future simulations will include antennas with more complex structures and characteristics. The height of the transmitter antennas with respect to surface level and their output powers are shown in Table 5.1.

Moreover, the four scenarios were populated with 500 receivers acting as A-IoT devices in the simulation, aiming to obtain a significant sample for statistical analysis and cover the entire area of the simulated scenarios (including building roofs). Similarly to the transmitters, the receivers' antennas can also be flexibly configured. For this first simulations, the receivers' antennas consist of a single isotropic element with a sensitivity of -100 dBm.

In order to evaluate and compare the channels computed by the ray tracing algorithms, a 5G NR-compliant OFDM signal with a BW of ~ 10 MHz, a sub-carrier spacing of 15 KHz and a RF

carrier of 3.5 GHz is transmitted. Two different modulations are used for this simulations: BPSK and quadrature amplitude modulation. In addition to the ray tracing channel, an AWGN channel with SNR values of 15 dB, 10 dB, and 5 dB is included. After simulating the transmission, the experimental BER cumulative distribution function (CDF) are calculated, allowing all scenarios of interest to be compared. Results are shown in Figure 5.8.

The results from the simulation show similar results for all the scenarios in terms of received signal quality. For BPSK signals ($M=2$) transmitted from both single-element ($T_x=1$) and two-element ($T_x=2$) antennas, and for SNR values of 15 dB and 10 dB, BER is under 10^{-5} in between 85 % and 90 % of the cases. This probability worsens with SNRs of 5 dB. In these cases, in 90 % of the cases BER is below 10^{-3} , and only in half of the cases BER is better than $2 \cdot 10^{-4}$. For quadrature amplitude modulation signals ($M=4$), results show worse behaviour of the transmitted signals. For SNRs of 15 dB, BER is below 10^{-5} in between 75 % and 80 % of the cases. For SNRs of 10 dB, BER is below 10^{-4} in ~ 75 % and below 10^{-5} in ~ 35 % of the cases. For SNRs of 5 dB, the signal quality is drastically reduced, obtaining a BER lower than 10^{-2} in ~ 70 % of the cases and under $6 \cdot 10^{-4}$ in only ~ 10 % of the cases. It is important to note that the BER results are computed considering only the receivers that have at least one possible path from the transmitter, removing all receivers out of coverage from the analysis.

In terms of radio coverage, the obtained results vary considerably depending on the scenario. The worse case is the RMa scenario due to its large dimensions, with 30.6 % of the receiver under coverage (i.e. with at least one path from the transmitter). For the UMa and UMi scenarios, 59.4 % and 76 % of the receivers have a connection with the transmitter, respectively, and finally, in the indoor office scenario, 98.4 % of receivers are connected to the transmitter.

The channels computed, tested, and presented in this section will be used to feed an A-IoT network simulator, allowing us to test the behavior of different MAC strategies in different scenarios in terms of data rate, latency, energy efficiency, and reliability. The results from this A-IoT network simulator will be presented in future deliverables.

Figure 5.8: Results of the simulated signal transmission through the channels computed by ray tracing algorithms in realistic scenarios. Each row presents results for a scenario of interest, and each column.

Chapter 6

Goal/context-aware protocols

This chapter explores the evolution of network architecture and management operations tailored for ENDS in 6G A-IoT networks. We depart from traditional QoS-centric designs towards goal- and context-aware, energy-efficient operations across END-RAN domains, also involving CN functions. The chapter starts by proposing and discussing context-aware solutions that enhance system dependability with minimal control-plane overhead while presenting performance evaluation results in representative use cases. Then, the focus shifts to two specific setups: i) ENDS sensing the occurrence of “events” in a non-isotropic manner, and ii) ENDS in a control system with goal-oriented scheduling for minimizing actuation error. We conclude the chapter by discussing potential enhancements to the 3GPP-defined AIOTF.

6.1 Context-aware protocols for dependable ENDS

Dependable operation in low-power, energy-constrained ENDS deployments cannot be achieved with static and context-agnostic protocols [137]. Reliable services under uncertainty require context awareness: devices and coordinators must sense and exploit what is known about energy state, information freshness, task relevance, and physical conditions to adjust the communication/sensing/computing/actuation tasks in real time. This section discusses a context-aware protocol design in which an edge-centric control plane aggregates lightweight telemetry and maps cross-layer context to dependability objectives (i.e., availability, reliability, timeliness, and resilience). This contextual information is then used to obtain per-device policies, wherein ENDS execute fast local actions at fine scales.

A simple, two-step field structure distinguishes between static hardware and operational descriptors, such as energy storage, computing, radio, memory, and sensors, from dynamic, application-specific fields. The latter provides the context necessary for the real-time adaptation of end-task executions, enabling tailored contextual performance for each use case. This separation reduces control overhead while enabling multiple forms of awareness to co-exist. Four complementary context dimensions influence task execution decisions. These include energy, freshness, task, and physical/medium awareness.

- **Energy awareness:** captures residual energy, EH and load dynamics to guide duty cycling, sensing frequency, and wake-up request aggressiveness. See already some examples in Sections 5.3 and 5.4.

- **Freshness awareness:** models timeliness via AoI-type metrics and can be used to align scheduling or contention priorities according to the most stale or most valuable information. See already one example in Section 5.5.
- **Task awareness:** filters and prioritizes task executions that meaningfully affect the application, using value-of-information notions to avoid spending energy on low-impact tasks.
- **Physical awareness:** exposes device health, channel quality, interference level, and (when available or predicted) CSI, allowing robust link selection, rate/power adaptation, and early fault detection.

Encoding energy, freshness, task, and physical context into the protocol, and letting an edge controller translate that context into per-device policies executed locally, yields dependable performance with modest control overhead. As discussed in the following, the application of context awareness to goal-oriented monitoring and AoI-sensitive status updates reduces latency/misses and increases availability/operational lifetime in ENDs, respectively.

We consider three representative scenarios to demonstrate how leveraging varied forms of context awareness can significantly enhance system dependability while imposing only minimal control-plane overhead. A pictorial representation of all three scenarios is provided in Figure 6.1.

Figure 6.1: Illustrative examples of context-awareness for dependable IoT. ED stands for event-driven.

6.1.1 Event-driven sensing

In the event-driven sensing scenario, the activity of ENDs is dictated by their proximity to critical events. At the occurrence of an event, the edge node may send wake-up signals to those idle/sleeping ENDs that are close to the event location and have higher energy levels. Herein, the duty cycling durations for the wake-up signals are critical to the latency and event's miss-detections. In this scenario, the context refers to the spatial and time correlation between ENDs and the events. To improve dependability, we propose a scheme combining RL and KNN to dynamically adjust duty cycling. It is assumed that 1% of the storage energy is consumed

for sensing and computing, while 10% is consumed for transmitting. As highlighted in Figures 6.2 and 6.3, the dependability performance, in terms of event detection probability/latency, and mean time to failure (MTTF), improves significantly with the proposed context-aware approach. Specifically, the probability of event detection and latency improve by 3 times and 56%, respectively, and MTTF improves by at least an order of magnitude. Finally, Figure 6.4 shows that mean availability also improves by about 10% under various coverage requirements.

Figure 6.2: Probability and latency of event detection for a context-aware approach and a context-agnostic benchmark as a function of the IoT density. The benchmark relies solely on spatial correlation for wake-up requests, while duty-cycle parameters are fixed via brute-force tuning to the event statistics.

6.1.2 Dynamic process/environment monitoring

A dynamic process state is represented in the form of a vector consisting of multiple state components, each observed by a single IoT. The edge node (EdN) responds to queries asked by the external server(s) and aims to minimize the MSE in the query response. Herein, a query refers to a request to send information about the particular characteristic of the dynamic process state. It is assumed that EdN is equipped with a state estimator of the dynamic process and is not aware of the time steps at which queries would be asked. The task-aware device scheduling problem is modeled as a partially observable Markov decision process, wherein the EdN acts as the *agent* with *action* space $\{0, 1, \dots, N\}$, where *action* $n \in \{1, \dots, N\}$ means polling device n , and *action* 0 means refraining from polling [138]. The agent's *state* is a function of (i) the prior (before IoT transmission) estimates obtained from the state estimator, (ii) the MSE in query response with respect to the prior estimates, and (iii) the query-related parameter such as the time elapsed since the last query from an external server [138]. We consider a non-linear dynamic process [138], non-linear observation model on IoT, cubature quadrature Kalman filter as state estimator on the EdN, and a RL-based task-aware device scheduler with the aforementioned partially observable Markov decision process *state/action/reward*. For comparison, a Monte Carlo scheduler is considered, which polls IoTs only when a query arrives. Figure 6.5 illustrates that the task-aware device scheduler reduces both the average query response time and the

Figure 6.3: MTTF in seconds for a context-aware approach and a context-agnostic benchmark as a function of the IoT density. The benchmark relies solely on spatial correlation for wake-up requests, while duty-cycle parameters are fixed via brute-force tuning to the event statistics.

Figure 6.4: Mean availability for a context-aware approach and a context-agnostic benchmark as a function of the IoT density.

Figure 6.5: Illustration of MTTF, total energy consumed at IoT devices, and average query response time during the test run of the task-aware device scheduler and the Monte Carlo scheduler from [138]. Here, E_0 is the energy consumed, per transmission, at the device. Moreover, the latency of the device-to-edge, edge-to-device, and edge-to-server transmission is 1 ms.

total energy consumed by IoT devices compared to the Monte Carlo scheduler. Moreover, Figure 6.5 illustrates MTTF is significantly better for the task-aware scheduler. Overall, the task-aware device scheduler [138] increases both the *reliability* and *availability*, the dependability attributes of the dynamic process monitoring system.

6.1.3 Request-based activation

In the request-based activation scenario, N devices communicate with a EdN over F channels. When an IoT device monitors its process, it generates a new packet. This monitoring can be done either with a given probability p , or when requested by the EdN. For simplicity, the channel undergoes on-off fading. Specifically, a IoT device has a connection to the EdN in a given channel at a given time-slot with probability $1 - \epsilon$, and does not have it with probability ϵ . Moreover, transmissions fail in a channel when there are collisions from two or more non-erased packets. Next, we compare three approaches of AoI-based scheduling, namely the optimal and autonomous scheduling and the threshold-based. In optimal scheduling, EdN selects the highest-ranked device among those with non-erased channels. In autonomous scheduling, IoT devices transmit a request to send signal. The request to send signal is preceded by a waiting time that is inversely proportional to AoI. Finally, in threshold-based scheme, IoT device decides to transmit if AoI is higher than a certain threshold. The average AoI performance of these schemes with respect to p is compared in Figure 6.6. The performance of the autonomous scheme is identical to the optimal scheme for large values of p , albeit requiring negligible overhead. However, the performance of the threshold-based scheme depends on the chosen threshold. The choice between these approaches depends on the characteristics of the network and the capabilities of the device. For example, if packets are generated frequently, then the autonomous scheme can be advantageous.

In contrast, if the packets are generated at will and IoT-D, EdN can afford the overhead, then the optimal scheme is a good choice. Finally, if communication between entities is not possible, then the threshold-based scheme can be used.

Figure 6.6: Comparison of three AoI-based approaches as function of the probability of activation p for a network with $N = 32$ IoT-Ds, $F = 2$ channels, and $\varepsilon = 0.5$.

6.2 Duty cycling and wake-up under non-isotropic sensing

Here, we present and address the challenge of END capability and context-aware data transmission design. Assuming a use case incorporating multiple ENDs, the goal is to design the data transfer duty cycle of each involved END in a goal-oriented way (i.e., to detect and identify an object or human as early as possible prior to entering a protected area), while considering different END target detection capabilities. To minimize energy, communication, and computation resource consumption per involved END, apart from END duty cycle design, data preparation at END is also subject to optimization. In particular, the number of transmissions and payload size per transmission should be minimized without (or only minimally) affecting the effectiveness of target detection goal accomplishment.

State-of-the-art solutions, such as [124], [125], typically consider an event type (e.g., motor temperature increase) and its detection by nearby ENDs, which experience it instantaneously and isotropically. However, it is argued that a scenario involving multiple moving targets calls for more advanced sensing power functions that incorporate additional arguments beyond the distance from the “epicenter” of the event. In such a scenario, targets may have a planned trajectory, i.e., known to the facility management, or an unknown trajectory, and need to be tracked in both cases. In such a setting, the deployed ENDs may have onboard cameras, each with its particular field of view, as shown in Figure 6.7 in more detail for a particular END and in Figure 6.8 in the context of a geo-fencing scenario. Hence, ENDs clustering (or ordering) should be performed in a way that adapts to the expected trajectory of the object. In case of

Figure 6.7: Detection sector of an END (e.g., camera) showing the object trajectory, entry and exit points, along with the angular and radial constraints.

multiple objects moving in the monitored area with uncorrelated trajectories, multiple distinct END clusters need to be considered. In case trajectories are significantly correlated, a single END cluster can suffice for END wake-up activations (gradually over time). This will introduce a sort of “detection multiplexing gain”, wherein a camera has the capability to correctly label the two objects within the same set of monitoring frames.

Given the described system setup, the objective is to ensure that END wake-up/sleep cycles are scheduled in such a way that an object is correctly classified with high confidence and for the majority of its trajectory (e.g., above 90%) within a facility area. Field-of-view overlaps may be beneficial in enhancing object classification confidence. A successful object detection event is declared by a fusion center by obtaining the multiple END detection task updates as soon as any of them locally detects the object and optionally assigns a classification label (e.g., “human”, “vehicle”, “animal”). Beyond that point in time, the ENDS do not need to adapt their camera activity profile, EH pattern, and detection result upload in the uplink to this object’s motion over, as this object has already been detected and identified. They should, of course, do so for other, still non-detected objects. Of course, these END operation parameters should be further adapted to the motion of the target in case the goal of the END network would be to continuously track the object until it departs the frontier of a given (e.g., protected or geo-fenced) area. Such a continuous tracking feature will be covered in future work.

The optimization problem of END energy consumption subject to a maximum allowable loss/delay of system updates as needed to effectively address the specific geo-fencing requirement is investigated. For smart logistics/warehousing use cases, intrusion detection is a functionality of paramount importance to ensure secure storage of goods in warehouses and other restricted areas of a production or logistics facility.

To address the problem of optimally deploying and controlling the duty cycle of the involved ENDS over time and for different intrusion trajectories, we propose a reward-based policy update

Figure 6.8: In-context activation of directional ENDs to ensure timely object detection - active ENDs in red color, idle ENDs in green color and sleeping ENDs in grey color.

scheme. The objective is to detect an intruder while the intruder is outside the perimeter of a protected area (detected with timeliness), while ensuring that the energy storage element of each involved ENDs is not depleted during the service time. The essential elements to formulate the proposed policy update scheme are the following:

- *the system state*, i.e., the state of the ENDs at a given time t . END state variables can be its position (unless there is only one option for its deployment), the orientation of the directional sensor (camera), the activity state of the camera (it is assumed that an always-on presence sensor can trigger the camera to switch on when needed), as well as the state of the communication module of the END (i.e., uploading data or being idle), along with its energy level and the intrusion detection state with a confidence level.
- a *set of actions* to be performed across the ENDs to meet the intrusion detection goal, i.e., bringing the system to a termination state where at least one END has successfully detected an intruder with a sufficient confidence level. Such actions, for one or multiple ENDs are: re-deploying the END (if this is possible), rotating the camera of the END, uploading the latest local detection results, waking up or putting the END to sleep.
- a *reward function* capturing both the level of effectiveness (accuracy and timeliness) in addressing the intrusion detection task and the energy cost to accomplish this goal. In the case when the intruder is detected only after entering the area, the combination of END wake-up patterns for this detection period is half-rewarded (detected but outdated). Worst-case scenario is when the intruder is not detected at all, then the action (END wake up patterns) is penalized.

One way to choose an initial state is to start with a grid-like END deployment and update it over time and per intrusion detection feedback. For exploration purposes during initial deployment calibration, the operator can mimic the behavior of an intruder in different ways (e.g., following trajectories) to ensure that the resulting policy generalizes sufficiently.

Figure 6.9: END equipped with a directional sensor (camera) and object/ human identification model to assist an intrusion detection service.

Note that the placement of ENDS may influence the EH performance. That is the case, for instance, for RF-EH, wherein the efficiency depends on the distance between the RF signal transmitter and the END. A simple scenario is where the AP is the main source of RF energy. In general, the ENDS need to be placed in such a way that the intruder is detected with high confidence as soon as possible, while, at the same time, it needs to be ensured that the “critical” ENDS for such detection are powered for as long as needed. Figure 6.9 shows a proposed architecture of the END considered for this scenario. It should be noted that the decision for END camera activation/deactivation or for video frame data buffering can be triggered by a controller as part of an intrusion detection system operating in the network or by a local agent tracking identification task start and progression.

Details of the policy updating scheme and numerical evaluation results focusing on metrics, such as the total energy consumed per accomplished task, are planned for D3.2.

6.3 Goal-oriented scheduling in a control system

In this section, the problem of scheduling ENDS to effectively support goal-aware actuation decisions in a closed-loop control system is formulated.

Consider the goal-oriented control system, illustrated in Figure 6.10, consisting of ENDS, an edge node, and an actuator. A cubature quadrature Kalman filter-based state estimator, END scheduler, and controller are present at the edge node. ENDS with indices $n \in \{1, 2, \dots, N\}$ observe a non-linear dynamic process (NLDP), whose state is denoted as $\mathbf{x}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^{M \times 1}$. The dynamic process evolves as follows [139], [140]

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{x}(t) &= \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}(t-1)) + \mathbf{B} \cdot \mathbf{u}(\mathbf{x}(t-1)) + \mathbf{v}_1(t) \in \mathbb{R}^{M \times 1}, \\ \mathbf{y}(t) &= \mathbf{g}(\mathbf{x}(t)) + \mathbf{v}_2(t) \in \mathbb{R}^{M \times 1}. \end{aligned} \quad (6.1)$$

where $\mathbf{v}_1(t) \sim \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{0}_M, \mathbf{\Sigma}_{v_1})$ and $\mathbf{v}_2(t) \sim \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{0}_M, \mathbf{\Sigma}_{v_2})$ denotes the Gaussian noises, $\mathbf{B} \cdot \mathbf{u}(\mathbf{x}(t-1))$ is the *actuation*, $\mathbf{B} \in \mathbb{R}^{M \times M}$, $\mathbf{u}(\cdot) \in \mathbb{R}^{M \times 1}$ is the control input, $\mathbf{f}(\cdot)$ is the non-linear dynamic process (NLDP), $\mathbf{g}(\cdot)$ is END’s non-linear observation model, and $\mathbf{y}(t)$ is the observation at ENDS. Examples of real non-linear dynamic processes are available in [140].

Figure 6.10: Illustration of the goal-oriented control system. ENDs are observing a NLDP. The edge node polls ENDs as well as sends the control input to the actuator, which later performs the actuation on the NLDP.

The cubature quadrature Kalman filter-based state estimator remotely estimates the state of the NLDP and encompasses two steps: *prediction* and *update*. The *prediction* step computes the prior estimates $\{\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{pri}(t), \Psi_{pri}(t)\}$. Next, if an END is polled by the scheduler, the state estimator advances to the *update* step, which leads to the posterior estimates $\{\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{pos}(t), \Psi_{pos}(t)\}$. Otherwise, $\{\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{pos}(t), \Psi_{pos}(t)\} = \{\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{pri}(t), \Psi_{pri}(t)\}$. Here, $\{\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{pos}(t), \hat{\mathbf{x}}_{pri}(t)\}$ are mean vectors, while $\{\Psi_{pos}(t), \Psi_{pri}(t)\}$ are covariance matrices.

The controller is event-triggered and sends the control input $\mathbf{u}(\cdot)$ to the actuator, where

$$\mathbf{u}(\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{pos}(t), \Psi_{pos}(t)) = \begin{cases} \mathbf{0}_M, & \theta \geq \xi(\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{pos}(t), \Psi_{pos}(t)), \\ \mathbf{a}(\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{pos}(t), \Psi_{pos}(t)), & \theta < \xi(\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{pos}(t), \Psi_{pos}(t)). \end{cases} \quad (6.2)$$

Here θ is sampled from a uniform distribution in the interval $[0, 1]$, $\mathbf{a}(\cdot)$ is a non-linear control function, and $\xi(\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{pos}(t), \Psi_{pos}(t)) = \mathbb{E}(\mathbb{I}(\max(0, |\hat{\mathbf{x}}(t)| - \eta) > 0))$ is the probability of actuation with respect to the posterior estimates [139], where $\hat{\mathbf{x}}(t) = \mathcal{N}(\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{pos}(t), \Psi_{pos}(t))$ is a sample with respect to the posterior estimates.

Note that the goal in the aforementioned control system is to minimize the MSE in the actuation operation, along with reducing the number of sensor polling instances. The MSE in the actuation operation is defined as

$$\text{MSE}_a(\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{pos}(t), \Psi_{pos}(t)) = \mathbb{E}((\mathbf{B}\mathbf{u}(\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{pos}(t), \Psi_{pos}(t)) - \mathbf{B}\mathbf{u}(\mathbf{x}(t)))^2). \quad (6.3)$$

Next, the ENDs scheduling problem can be defined as a Markov decision process with *action* space $\mathcal{A} = \{0, 1, \dots, N\}$. Here, action $p(t) = n \in \{1, \dots, N\}$ signifies END n is polled at t , while $p(t) = 0$ signifies ENDs are not polled. The *state* of the Markov decision process is $\{\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{pri}(t), \Psi_{pri}(t), \text{MSE}_a(\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{pri}(t), \Psi_{pri}(t)), \xi(\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{pri}(t), \Psi_{pri}(t)), (1 - \xi(\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{pri}(t), \Psi_{pri}(t)))\}$. Meanwhile, the *reward* of the Markov decision process is

$$\begin{aligned} r_p(t) = & \mathbb{I}(p == 0) \left(-10^{\mathbb{I}(\theta \leq \xi(\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{pos}(t), \Psi_{pos}(t)))} \text{MSE}_a(\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{pos}(t), \Psi_{pos}(t)) \right) \\ & + \mathbb{I}(p != 0) \left(10^{\mathbb{I}(\theta \leq \xi(\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{pos}(t), \Psi_{pos}(t)))} (\text{MSE}_a(\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{pri}(t), \Psi_{pri}(t)) \right. \\ & \left. - \text{MSE}_a(\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{pos}(t), \Psi_{pos}(t))) - d_{tx} \right). \end{aligned} \quad (6.4)$$

As $\mathbf{a}(\cdot)$ is a non-linear function, it is not possible to devise a closed-form expression of $\text{MSE}_a(\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{pos}(t), \Psi_{pos}(t))$. Thus, we propose to solve the aforementioned scheduling problem using deep reinforcement learning. The implementation of the deep reinforcement learning-based scheduler and simulation results will be provided in D3.2.

6.4 Enhanced AIOTF for connect-compute assignment

In this section, an enhanced version of 3GPP AIOTF is proposed to assist an application service provider with achieving its application goals efficiently by assigning networking and computing tasks over one or multiple END deployment areas.

6.4.1 Background, motivation and challenges

In mobile communications systems up to LTE, network architecture was designed aiming at ensuring a minimum level of QoS for each connected device. In other words, the design goal was to approach a fixed, prescribed network coverage and capacity requirement. This approach was based on the assumption that a user may demand service at any time and in any place. However, the *context* of the service request was significantly overlooked. For example, communication reliability is far more significant when the device is part of a roadside scenario, as compared to a handheld device used for entertainment purposes in a domestic setting.

Figure 6.11: A-IoT system architecture (non-roaming), as defined in [141].

The proliferation of 5G and its penetration into vertical industries (besides continuing to serve individual subscribers) created the need for the placement of *task-aware* communication and workload processing functionality throughout the continuum involving the device, RAN, CN and the network orchestration and management functions. According to this approach, signaling and processing are *purposed* functionalities, and the available resources should be allocated to these functionalities to effectively address the purpose of signaling and processing instead of aiming at fulfilling static QoS requirements.

However, from an IoT device point of view, commercialized 5G systems are based on devices that contain battery elements. Although 3GPP specification work on service requirements and architectural support for A-IoT devices and their use have begun in the 3GPP standard during its Rel. 19 work [141], [142], where the main new functional entity is the AIOTF (see Figure 6.11), the impact on network architecture across its domains still needs to be defined in more detail from

a functional entity, interface and protocol standpoint. The additional architectural challenge, as compared to 5G communications, is to enhance the AIOTF and the interfaces related to it in order for the network to orchestrate not only radio and computing resources across ENDS, involving the edge or remote cloud as well, but also the ambient energy that ENDS need to effectively manage when executing the application task tailored to the A-IoT use case, as the ones identified in [143].

Towards this end, a hierarchical, cross-domain approach is proposed in this section for efficient and effective networking and computing functionality placement that is both energy and task-aware. Main new functionalities of the proposed approach are: i) the energy-aware decoupling of a service-related task into communication and computation actions, and ii) the enablement of monitoring task progression and END energy availability for multiple tasks in a service area. These functionalities may be enhancements to the AIOTF or a different CN function or management function. The proposed solution may apply to various AMBIENT-6G scenarios involving ENDS, e.g., Cooperative Mobile Robots and Smart Agriculture, in indoor or outdoor settings.

Figure 6.12: System setup. Each END area of interest may be characterized by different A-IoT service requirements.

6.4.2 System setup

We consider an A-IoT system setup composed of a set of ENDS operating over a deployment area, such as a factory floor, a warehouse (indoor) or a crop field (outdoor). Each of these ENDS is capable of performing at least one (vertical) task function, namely, sensing, communication, actuation, data processing, data aggregation, and even AI inference, self-monitoring and local decision making. Of course, the capability of a given END to perform a task function depends on the END class it belongs to (cf. D2.1 [1]).

At the network infrastructure side, we assume that one or more instances of an AIOTF, as

defined in [141], are deployed, where each instance is tailored to one or multiple particular geographical areas of interest. Further, as a 3rd party business entity, an application service provider sets the overall goal per which the ENDS should operate. In line with [141], this entity is represented by an application function (AF) which, after following an authentication and authorization procedure, can interact with one or more discovered AIOTF instances via the network exposure function. Figure 6.12 illustrates the considered system setup.

Given the described A-IoT system setup, along with the function of the AIOTF and the A-IoT services defined in [141], the proposal is to identify gaps in these definitions, as driven by the need the network has to support joint networking and computing functionality placement across the continuum of deployed ENDS and the edge cloud hosting functionality that can be assumed collocated with each AP providing coverage and capacity to the involved ENDS. Such placement will need to be both energy-aware and application/service-aware. In deliverable D3.2, a signaling framework involving the enhanced AIOTF and relevant new data structures will be proposed to address this problem.

Chapter 7

Threat analysis and lightweight security protocol designs

ENDs stretch 6G far beyond conventional cellular IoT: they harvest energy, operate on microwatt budgets, and will be deployed at a massive scale. These constraints force new communication and trust models, not retrofits, and make security-by-design essential: authentication, integrity, and privacy must be embedded from the outset rather than added later. Current standardization (e.g., Rel. 19 studies on passive/backscatter and EH devices, with broader scope heading into Rel.20) highlights both the enlarged attack surface and the need for simplified yet effective protections. In this chapter, a systematic threat-analysis process (data-flow mapping, asset identification, adversary modeling, and STRIDE/attack-tree assessment) will be applied to two representative pillars: a PLA for ultra-passive BDs, and a secure-update path that traces boot, keying, and firmware delivery while accounting for energy costs across device classes. At this initial stage, our goal is to set the foundations rather than present final results. The outcome is a prioritized risk register with concrete mitigations and KPIs that keep protections effective and energy-proportionate across Classes 1–4 defined in D2.1 [1].

7.1 Threat analysis process and procedures

Since ENDs are ultra-low power, subject to energy-availability constraints, while integrated into different verticals, a secure-by-design thinking is a must. To implement security by design, there is a need for threat analysis and risk assessment for newly introduced protocols and designs, ensuring that authentication, confidentiality, integrity, and privacy mitigations are not retrofitted but rather embedded from the outset. The limitations of A-IoT devices will introduce large-scale attack surfaces due to device density and lifecycle management challenges (e.g., onboarding and key provisioning). Therefore, the related security specification in 3GPP is not only about adapting existing frameworks but also about defining new protocols and trust models that can maintain security while accommodating the functional constraints introduced by the energy constraints of these devices.

In Rel.19, 3GPP started exploring use cases, deployment scenarios, connectivity topologies, KPIs, and air-interface design targets for passive ENDs. Rel.19 [144] started assessing security aspects such as authentication, confidentiality, and simplified cryptographic mechanisms already from the outset. Moving towards Rel.20, the scope of A-IoT in 3GPP is expanded by including

enhanced topologies, more capable device types, and integration into system architecture along with ongoing work in SA2 and SA3. This progression underscores the need for threat analysis and risk assessment from the beginning of the design process.

7.1.1 Threat modeling and risk assessment

Threat modeling is the process of systematically identifying and prioritizing potential threats to a system. It is typically applied during system design to identify potential threats and determine appropriate mitigations. In the AMBIENT-6G project, we aim to conduct threat modeling on some of the proposed concepts (e.g., PLA). The outcome of the threat modeling will help to improve the overall security posture of both solutions. The following threat analysis steps will be adopted to guide us:

- (i) **Data flow diagrams (DFDs):** DFDs are diagrams that show the interactions and how data and information is exchanged between different components and assets within a system. They also define trust boundaries, dividing the system into trust domains, within which assets share trust assumptions.
- (ii) **Assets:** Assets are defined as critical elements of a system that require protection. Normally, assets are classified by their value and impact of loss on an organization in case of compromise or unavailability. An asset can be a component, data, a person, or a resource.
- (iii) **Adversary model:** An adversary model is a list of potential adversaries who may be interested in attacking a system based on motives such as political or financial. Normally, we define two types of adversaries: insiders, with the assumption that the adversary is already inside the system, and outsiders, who are adversaries that want to exploit a vulnerability to gain access to the system. The correct definition of the adversary model helps to prioritize threats and determine the appropriate mitigations.
- (iv) **Threat Analysis:** Once the preparatory steps have been completed, threat analysis can be performed using an established threat modeling framework. One widely used framework is STRIDE [145], introduced by Microsoft in 1999. STRIDE is an acronym for Spoofing, Tampering, Repudiation, Information Disclosure, Denials of Service, and Elevation of Privileges. It classifies threats by attacker method and by the security property affected (authentication, integrity, non-repudiation, confidentiality, availability, and authorization). In practice, STRIDE is applied to DFDs to systematically identify potential threats and derive attack scenarios, followed by defining the appropriate mitigations.

Next, we describe the planned application of threat analysis on selected use-cases.

7.1.2 Threat modeling for PLA for BDs

There is an ongoing effort to define a novel PLA protocol for BDs. Threat modeling is essential as a core design phase to provide a systematic methodology to anticipate and prioritize potential adversarial actions, ensuring the resilience of the protocol against potential threats. Why is threat modeling important in this use case? Some answers are given below.

- (i) **Guide Security-Centric Design:** PLA schemes are optimized for performance (e.g., throughput, energy efficiency), and threat modeling ensures that the design process takes into account potential attacks and does not only focus on optimization.

- (ii) **Address Vulnerabilities:** BDs cannot implement heavyweight crypto due to constraints in power, memory, and processing capabilities. Threat modeling will help with identifying which lightweight PHY countermeasures are effective against identified threats.
- (iii) **Risk Assessment:** Not all threats have equal likelihood or impact. Threat modeling provides a structured way to quantify risks and define mitigations taking into account device capabilities.
- (iv) **Validation and Standardization:** Threat models provide proofs to demonstrate the security guarantees. This transparency is critical for the adoption by stakeholders and standardization bodies.

7.2 Energy impact of security protocols

The feasibility of security mechanisms in ENDS is shaped by their energy budgets. D2.1 [1] distinguishes four categories: (i) *ultra-passive devices*, which lack meaningful storage beyond transient capacitances; (ii) *duty-cycled barebone devices*, powered intermittently by small buffers; (iii) *duty-cycled persistent devices*, equipped with rechargeable storage for scheduled operation; and (iv) *continuous-operation devices*, sustained by long-term storage and capable of semi-continuous functioning. Each category affords a distinct envelope of cryptographic possibilities, from minimal PHY protection to full-stack end-to-end protocols, as discussed below.

- Class 1: ultra-passive devices

Ultra-passive devices represent the lower bound of this spectrum. Despite their lack of dedicated energy reserves, they can support cryptographic primitives when externally powered, provided that the functions are implemented in hardware. Examples are RFID and NFC tags, which harvest energy from a reader's electromagnetic field and rely on integrated accelerators for cryptography. ISO/IEC 29167 specifies advanced encryption standard (AES)-128 as suitable for such tags [146], enabling challenge–response or stream cipher–based authentication within the narrow time window of energization. Measurements confirm that hardware execution of AES-128 or comparable block ciphers consumes only a few microjoules per block (see Figure 7.1), making it possible to provide authentication and lightweight confidentiality even under transient powering. However, session-based security such as transport layer security (TLS) or datagram transport layer security (DTLS) remains infeasible. Their reliance on multi-round negotiation, certificate handling, and kilobytes of message exchange [147] far exceeds the capacity of a device that operates only while in the reader's field. Security in this category is therefore localized and reader-assisted, with cryptographic strength confined to hardware-accelerated primitives executed on demand [148].

- Class 2: duty-cycled barebone devices

Devices with short-term storage, namely duty-cycled barebone devices, extend these capabilities by introducing a small buffer that allows bursty computation and radio communication. They employ the same hardware-accelerated symmetric ciphers as ultra-passive devices, but under device-controlled duty cycles rather than strictly reader-assisted operation. Importantly, their energy budget allows occasional use of asymmetric operations, provided these are not repeated frequently. In practice, such devices rely on long-term

Figure 7.1: Measured energy consumption of hardware-accelerated encryption and decryption operations on the Silicon Labs EFM32FG23A microcontroller for different cryptographic algorithms.

keys that are refreshed only occasionally, not at every communication session. This approach reduces the overhead of repeated negotiation while still making periodic key renewal possible for resilience.

LoRaWAN exemplifies this model. Devices are provisioned with two root keys (AppKey and NwkKey) and execute an over-the-air authentication procedure to derive session keys (AppSKey and NwkSKey) using AES-128 [149]. The join procedure is relatively expensive, requiring data exchanges and cryptographic computations, but is performed infrequently (e.g., once at boot or periodically after many sessions). During normal operation, uplink and downlink traffic are protected using AES-128 in counter mode with message integrity codes, which can be executed in microjoules when hardware support is available. This architecture aligns well with the duty-cycled barebone profile: asymmetric or session-level procedures are rare, while day-to-day communication relies on efficient symmetric cryptography with minimal overhead.

- Class 3: duty-cycled persistent devices

Duty-cycled persistent devices, with rechargeable long-term storage, enable more advanced security features to be integrated into their scheduled activity patterns. Their energy budget allows not only network-layer protection (e.g., DTLS for constrained application protocol (CoAP)) but also security at the application layer, such as message queuing telemetry transport (MQTT) secured by TLS. In this case, symmetric operations are well within budget, while session based asymmetric cryptography can be performed without exhausting the energy buffer, though at a noticeable cost. Measurements indicate that a single TLS handshake can consume several joules over cellular links, a cost that is sustainable when amortized over long connections but becomes prohibitive if repeated frequently. Persistent devices therefore support secure communications across multiple protocol layers, yet their energy profile requires careful balancing between frequency of rekeying, session lifetime, and overall device duty cycle.

- Class 4: continuous-operation devices

Continuous-operation devices complete the spectrum. Their sustained energy budgets allow them to implement the full security stack, from hardware-secured boot to application-layer protocols with certificate-based authentication. At this level, the energy cost of

cryptographic operations is marginal relative to baseline device consumption. Protocol selection nonetheless influences efficiency: for example, TLS over transmission control protocol consumes 10–20% more energy than DTLS over user datagram protocol in NB-IoT due to retransmissions and connection state maintenance.

In summary, hardware acceleration is what enables cryptography at the lowest end of the spectrum and remains a central enabler across categories. Ultra-passive devices demonstrate that, even without storage, optimized silicon can deliver symmetric authentication. Barebone devices extend this by combining symmetric protection with infrequent asymmetric operations and occasional rekeying, as seen in LoRaWAN. Persistent devices broaden the scope by securing application-layer protocols such as CoAP or MQTT, though session costs remain an important factor. Continuous-operation devices can sustain application-level protections without compromise and often serve as anchors for securing the broader IoT ecosystem.

7.3 PHY authentication of BDs

In certain topologies of Class 1 devices (ultra-passive ENDs), such as those relying on BC, processing and power limitations render even lightweight cryptographic primitives impractical. In these cases, PLA has emerged as a compelling alternative to conventional cryptographic approaches for securing resource-constrained BDs. Classical PLA divides into device-fingerprint methods, leveraging manufacturing imperfections, and channel-fingerprint methods, exploiting spatial decorrelation and fading. However, applying these solutions in realistic systems exposes several gaps: ambient interference scenarios mix the BD's reflections with unknown ambient signals, making fingerprint extraction and spoofing defense difficult; most schemes require complex analyzers or accurate channel estimation that BDs cannot support; mutual authentication is rarely realized, mobility (Doppler/fast fading) degrades reliability; and weak links in monostatic BC compress secure coverage. As deployments become decentralized (e.g., BD-to-BD) and energy budgets shrink, eavesdropping, replay, relay, and counterfeiting remain persistent threats. Recent studies articulate these limitations explicitly for AmBC, BD-to-BD settings, and monostatic/RIS-aided links, motivating new designs that (i) eliminate channel estimation at BDs, (ii) confine exchanges within channel coherence, (iii) harden against wireless attacks, and (iv) scale to many BDs. They also highlight that RIS can bolster RSS and observability of reliable physical attributes, while introducing security considerations if compromised. In the next, we will summarize our contribution of PLA in different BC systems.

7.3.1 PHY authentication in monostatic BC systems

Monostatic BC systems enable battery-free or ultra-low-power BDs to convey data by reflecting incident RF signals from a radio-frequency source (RFS). However, mutual authentication is an open issue, since resource-constrained BDs cannot conduct complex operations to extract an authentication fingerprint to verify the legitimacy of incoming signals. In addition, mobility and resistance to various wireless attacks is also a challenge. The openness of the wireless medium and the tight energy/computation budgets at BDs make upper-layer cryptography burdensome and leave systems exposed to eavesdropping, identity spoofing, replay, and counterfeiting. PLA is appealing, but most existing backscatter PLAs are one-sided (RFS authenticates BD only), accuracy degrades under mobility, and scalability to many BDs is rarely addressed. AuthScatter

Figure 7.2: System model of AmbAu and potential attacks.

[150] tackles these gaps with an accurate, robust, and scalable mutual authentication scheme that runs at PHY and offloads complexity to the RFS. It leverages channel reciprocity and coherence, plus random numbers as a one-time pad, to secure key exchange without channel estimation or heavy processing at the tag. AuthScatter further incorporates a re-authentication mechanism that aggregates multiple uncorrelated channel realizations to amplify security, and a time division duplexing -based batch framework to scale authentication across many tags with low latency. Extensive analysis and simulations show high authentication accuracy over diverse SNRs and mobility, and resilience to all four attack families.

As shown in Figure 7.2, the system consists of one RFS and multiple BDs operating in time division duplexing mode. Channels are narrowband, block-fading, and approximately reciprocal within the channel coherence time T_c . Let $h_{A,B}$ denote the complex channel from node A to node B , with $y_B = h_{A,B}S + n_B$, $n_B \sim \mathcal{CN}(0, \sigma^2)$, and $h_{A,B} \approx h_{B,A}$ during one authentication. Each BD i holds an upper-layer ID ID_i , a backscatter coefficient B_i , and a shared physical identity key K_i ; the RFS keeps its per-BD physical identity $K_{R,i}$. AuthScatter runs two tightly timed phases: (i) scrambling reference generation, where the RFS transmits a random challenge S , the BD reflects a random number D , and the RFS forms a complex reciprocal “scrambling reference” that will invert subsequent channel fading; (ii) physical identity exchange, where the RFS sends $K_{R,i}$ scrambled by that reference, enabling the BD to authenticate the RFS from harvested-power measurements. Upon success, the BD backscatters $\phi_D K_i$ so the RFS directly extracts K_i and authenticates the BD. Keys are then refreshed using D (and a lightweight symmetric step) to mitigate long-term leakage. Threats follow a standard adversary model covering eavesdropping, identity spoofing, replay, and counterfeiting, including near-field correlated channels; AuthScatter’s resilience is proved via mutual-information bounds and attack success probabilities.

In addition, weak direct links and rapid performance decay with distance make PLA fragile in practice for monostatic BC systems. Moreover, most backscatter PLAs are one-sided (reader→BD)

and struggle to realize mutual authentication under the tag's severe energy/computation limits. The work in [151] proposes a RIS-aided PLA that turns the propagation environment into part of the security mechanism: a RIS, operated near-optimally, simultaneously boosts the tag's harvested power and the reader's RSS, enabling robust mutual authentication and enlarging the effective secure coverage. The paper also provides a dual-edged security analysis, showing that while a trusted RIS strengthens PLA and secrecy, a compromised RIS can degrade both by steering energy away from the legitimate receiver or towards an eavesdropper. Extensive simulations quantify these effects via receiver operating characteristic curves (authentication rate vs. false acceptance) and average secrecy capacity.

7.3.2 PHY authentication in AmBC systems

AmBC enables battery-free or ultra-low-power BDs to harvest energy from ambient RF (e.g., WiFi/TV) and convey data by modulating reflections. However, the openness of the wireless medium and the tags' tight resource budgets expose AmBC to impersonation and wireless spoofing threats, while heavyweight cryptography is often impractical at the tag side. PLA is attractive because it leverages inherent signal/channel traits as fingerprints, but many existing methods either target monostatic settings or depend on channel estimation and costly analyzers that BDs cannot support in AmBC. AmbAu addresses this gap with a lightweight two-stage PLA that directly authenticates BDs by exploiting the correlation between the ambient source and the backscatter, shifting complexity to an independent multi-antenna verifier and avoiding channel estimation. The design includes a security analysis against replay, relay, and counterfeiting, and simulations show high accuracy and efficiency across SNRs and attacker placements.

Figure 7.3: System model of AmbAu.

As shown in Figure 7.3, we consider an AmBC system comprising an ambient RF source S , a passive BD B to be authenticated, and a verifier/receiver R equipped with a uniform linear array. Channels $h_{L,K}(t)$, $L, K \in \{S, B, R\}$, experience Rayleigh fading with carrier-offset phase and propagation delay, modeled as

$$h_{L,K}(t) = |h_{L,K}|e^{j\phi_{L,K}}\delta(t - \tau_{L,K}), \quad (7.1)$$

where $\phi_{L,K} \in [0, 2\pi]$ and $\tau_{L,K}$ denotes the $L \rightarrow K$ delay. The received baseband at R is the superposition of the direct ambient component, the BD's backscatter, and AWGN:

$$y(t) = \underbrace{\sqrt{P} h_{S,R}(t)s(t)}_{y_d(t)} + \underbrace{\sqrt{P\eta} h_{S,B}(t)h_{B,R}(t)s(t)}_{y_b(t)} + n(t), \quad (7.2)$$

where $s(t)$ has average power P , $\eta \in (0, 1]$ is the BD modulation loss, and $n(t) \sim \mathcal{CN}(0, \sigma^2)$. Equivalently, $y(t) = y_d(t) + y_b(t) + n(t)$.

AmbAu constructs a complex covariance fingerprint $\mathbf{R}_{B,S}$ from multi-antenna observations that capture the correlation structure between $y_b(t)$ and $y_d(t)$. During authentication, a fresh estimate $\widehat{\mathbf{R}}_{B,S}$ is compared to the stored fingerprint via an ℓ_1 decision rule:

$$\|\widehat{\mathbf{R}}_{B,S} - \mathbf{R}_{B,S}\|_1 \underset{\mathcal{H}_0}{\overset{\mathcal{H}_1}{\geq}} \delta, \quad (7.3)$$

where \mathcal{H}_1 denotes a legitimate BD, \mathcal{H}_0 an attacker, and δ is a threshold controlling the true/false positive rate trade-off. The test is robust because attacker signals traverse different (decorrelated) cascaded channels and thus yield covariance patterns that deviate from the whitelist. The primary complexity arises from covariance formation, $\mathcal{O}(LM^2)$ for signal length L and M antennas; authentication decisions execute in milliseconds.

7.3.3 PHY authentication in backscattering tag-to-tag networks

AmBC enables battery-free or ultra-low-power BDs to communicate by modulating and reflecting legacy RF signals (e.g., WiFi/TV) while harvesting energy. However, the broadcast medium, the lack of a dedicated reader in distributed AmBC, and the tags' extremely tight energy/computation budgets make classical cryptography heavy and leave systems exposed to impersonation, eavesdropping, replay, and counterfeiting. Most PHY authentication schemes for BC assumes monostatic reader-tag setups or relies on channel estimation and active transmissions, assumptions that do not hold for BD-to-BD authentication under ambient interference. To close this gap, we proposed a PHY challenge-response scheme [152] for AmBC systems that (i) embeds low-density physical identity keys as fingerprints, (ii) designs a joint transceiver that integrates the BD's backscatter waveform with receiver functionality to suppress ambient OFDM interference via cyclic prefix (CP) structure, and (iii) completes key exchanges within the channel coherence time using a random number to harden secrecy. Security analysis and simulations show high accuracy across SNRs and mobility and robustness against all four attack families, while keeping BD-side complexity minimal.

As shown in Figure 7.4, the system comprises a legacy OFDM ambient RF source S and two single-antenna BDs, BD_i (prover) and BD_j (verifier). Let $h_i(t)$, $h_j(t)$ denote downlink channels $S \rightarrow BD_i$, BD_j , and $h_{i,j}(t)$ the inward channel between the BDs. With backscatter coefficient $b_i(t)$ and ambient signal $s(t)$, the received baseband at BD_j is

$$y_j(t) = \underbrace{h_{i,j}(t)h_i(t)b_i(t)s(t)}_{y_{b,j}(t)} + \underbrace{h_j(t)s(t)}_{y_{d,j}(t)} + w_j(t), \quad (7.4)$$

or in discrete time $y_j[n] = y_{b,j}[n] + y_{d,j}[n] + w_j[n]$. Each BD contains an energy harvester, a backscatter modulator implementing M -amplitude shift keying via impedance states, a small memory storing physical identity keys, and an MCU capable of simple multiplications/divisions. PLCRA-BD engineers the BD waveform $b[n]$ to insert a mid-symbol amplitude hop within each

Figure 7.4: System model of PLCRA-BD.

OFDM symbol so that $y_{d,j}[n]$ retains the CP repetition while $y_{b,j}[n]$ does not. The verifier then cancels the downlink via CP subtraction, i.e.,

$$z_{b,j}[n] = y_j[n] - y_j[n + N] = h_{i,j}[n]h_i[n] B[n]\xi[n], \quad (7.5)$$

and estimates the message from the harvested power $P(z_{b,j}[n])$ without decoding or CSI. Synchronization uses the OFDM preamble or the CP periodicity. Precise mid-point switching is unnecessary provided the reversed/duplicated structure is preserved. The adversary model includes (i) upper-layer impersonation and (ii) wireless attacks, including naive eavesdropping, replay, and counterfeiting, while “smart” eavesdropping attacks within $\lambda/2$ are also considered but are practically detectable.

Backscattering tag-to-tag networks allow two passive tags to exchange data by modulating and reflecting an external RF field. Yet these networks inherit severe constraints: tags lack the energy/computation budget for cryptography or CSI-heavy signal processing; spectral efficiency and communication range are limited; and the open wireless medium invites impersonation, relay, and replay attacks. Prior PLA for backscatter largely targets reader-tag settings and does not translate to tag-to-tag operation under such constraints. In [153], we propose a voltage profile-driven PLA: each tag authenticates its peer using the unique output voltage profiles naturally generated by the tag’s power-harvesting and envelope-detector circuits, thus avoiding complex analyzers, explicit channel estimation, and heavy computation at the endpoints. To overcome low SNR and short range, an indoor RIS is integrated to shape propagation, boosting harvested power and RSS, and thereby improving PLA accuracy and extending secure coverage. Security analysis and simulations demonstrate robustness to common attacks and strong performance across distances, SNRs, and attacker placements.

Chapter 8

Conclusion

The work presented in this deliverable establishes the technical foundation for END communications and networking within the AMBIENT-6G framework. It synthesizes early research outcomes across communication, charging, operation, and security, providing the first step towards an integrated protocol and architecture stack for sustainable 6G END systems. The studies reported here address a wide spectrum of challenges inherent to END operation: energy scarcity, synchronization and connectivity reliability, scalability of dense deployments, and the trade-offs between communication efficiency, intelligence, and security.

8.1 Insights and lessons learnt

Chapter 2 examined the evolution of 3GPP A-IoT PHY mechanisms beyond Rel.19. It demonstrated that modest but well-targeted enhancements, such as CFO-aware synchronization and adaptive modulation, can significantly extend reliability and range while maintaining backward compatibility with Rel.19 devices. Furthermore, VLC-based synchronization was shown to provide an electromagnetic-interference-free timing alternative, particularly suitable for indoor scenarios requiring precise coordination among ENDS. A study of symbol-synchronous networking also revealed that multi-hop relaying combined with probabilistic sleeping can dramatically reduce latency and energy consumption in dense deployments. Together, these results delineate a coherent path towards scalable and robust PHY solutions for energy-neutral operation.

Chapter 3 focused on BC, assessing their feasibility and potential role as a key enabler of ultra-low-power connectivity. The chapter introduced a baseband-equivalent signal model that will underpin analytical and simulation studies in future phases, while also identifying the primary technical challenges in synchronization, interference management, and modulation. The presented investigations into symbiotic radio architectures and combined VLC/BC systems illustrated viable routes for integrating ENDS into existing wireless infrastructures without the need for dedicated spectrum. Overall, the findings emphasize that BC, particularly when tightly coupled with ambient illumination or RF carriers, constitutes a promising building block for large-scale, sustainable passive END connectivity.

Chapter 4 shifted the attention to RF-WPT systems and protocols. The work demonstrated that coherent BF protocols yield superior energy-delivery efficiency and fairness in large-scale deployments, albeit at the cost of synchronization and CSI overhead. Non-coherent and CSI-free

approaches, while simpler, plateau in achievable performance, highlighting the need for adaptive hybrid strategies. The analysis of waveform effects on rectifier behavior further suggests that average incident power, rather than PAPR, dominates EH efficiency in practical scenarios. These insights provide critical guidance for balancing complexity, synchronization, and efficiency in next-generation RF-charging protocols. The experimental results obtained from the Techtile testbed offer concrete evidence that WPT system performance strongly depends on infrastructure calibration and waveform choice, providing a solid empirical basis for future optimization and standardization efforts.

Chapter 5 considers policies applied at the MAC and RRC layers for ENDS. The enhancements in various aspects, including user privacy, channel access, and data preparation for transmission, are discussed. In contrast to conventional devices with relaxed energy limits, ENDS cannot use protocols with high signalling overhead and many retransmissions in case of transmission failures. Therefore, it is important that MAC protocols make energy-aware decisions, relying on the energy balance feedback loop and predictions, which are validated by several results. Furthermore, the chapter also delves into the challenges and complexity of the realistic simulation of A-IoT. Preliminary results of channel modeling in different realistic 3D environments are demonstrated, which will be used to feed an A-IoT network simulator.

Chapter 6 moved to higher-layer orchestration, presenting a forward-looking vision of intelligent network operation and management for ENDS. Herein, context-aware solutions were proposed to enhance system dependability with minimal control-plane overhead, and performance evaluation results were discussed in representative use cases. Several hybrid wake-up control schemes were proposed to maximize information yield under energy-autonomy constraints, exploiting spatial clustering and data-driven RL methods. The chapter further extended these ideas to closed-loop control systems, where deep RL will be considered for guiding energy-aware sensing schedules to minimize actuation error. Complementary to these, some enhancement of the AIOTF were proposed for dynamic and goal-oriented allocation of networking and computing tasks along the device-to-edge continuum. By integrating application objectives with the energy and communication states of deployed ENDS, the enhanced AIOTF enables adaptive placement of computation and data-processing functions, ultimately improving efficiency and responsiveness. Collectively, these contributions illustrate how intelligence, context awareness, and system-wide optimization can elevate END from purely reactive to purpose-driven operation.

Finally, Chapter 7 established the security foundations for ENDS within 6G ecosystems. It underscored the need for energy-proportionate and system-aware protection mechanisms that account for the diverse capabilities of the END classes. The developed threat-analysis framework, combining data-flow mapping, adversary modeling, and STRIDE-based assessment, provides a systematic way to identify and prioritize vulnerabilities across device categories. Complementary to this, energy-aware secure-update mechanisms were outlined, demonstrating that even ultra-passive ENDS can support lightweight authentication through hardware-assisted symmetric methods, while more capable ENDS can execute full cryptographic updates when properly scheduled. Furthermore, a suite of PLA schemes, AuthScatter for monostatic BC, AmbAu for AmBC, and PLCRA-BD for BD-to-BD authentication, were considered, showing that mutual authentication and robustness can be achieved without imposing heavy computational burdens. This security-by-design approach ensures that future END protocols maintain both trust and feasibility across the entire device spectrum.

8.2 Final remarks and the path to D3.2

The discussions and results throughout the deliverable are closely interconnected. Indeed, note that the developed low-power communication methods and energy-transfer protocols collectively define the operational envelope within which higher-layer networking, orchestration, and security solutions are conceived. The adopted cross-layer viewpoint ensures that progress in one area, such as waveform adaptation, energy control, or trust management, feeds into the design assumptions of the others. Overall, this deliverable marks a major milestone in defining the building blocks of low-power 6G network protocols and infrastructures. It suggests that cross-layer co-design, spanning PHY, MAC, architectural, charging, and security domains, is essential to achieving dependable, scalable, and sustainable END systems. The results collectively highlight the necessity of combining waveform intelligence, AmBC techniques, efficient WPT, adaptive scheduling, and lightweight security mechanisms under a unified design framework.

The next phase of work, culminating in D3.2, will advance these studies towards mature designs, deeper technical validation, and refined cross-layer understanding. We will transition from conceptual and early validation results toward advanced implementations and quantitative performance evaluations. Some work is specifically expected on refining the proposed AIOTF, WPT, and PLA mechanisms, developing deep-learning-based scheduling policies, and validating them through experimentation and system-level simulations.

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